

University of Twente

faculty of engineering technology

Engineering Fluid Dynamics Group

Discrete Exterior Calculus with applications in Fluid Dynamics

E. Hoogendoorn
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University of Twente

Faculty of Engineering Technology
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Engineering Fluid Dynamics Group

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DISCRETE EXTERIOR CALCULUS WITH APPLICATIONS IN FLUID DYNAMICS

E. Hoogendoorn

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Exam committee:

Prof.dr.ir. H.W.M. Hoeijmakers (afstudeerdocent)

Dr.ir. E.T.A. van der Weide (mentor)

Dr.ir. R. Hagmeijer

Dr. ir. O. Bokhove

PREFACE

This thesis is written in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Science in Mechanical Engineering at the University of Twente.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First, I'd like to thank my supervisors, for giving me the freedom to pursue my interests.

Remco Hartkamp, for putting up with my monologues on Cantor and infinity.

The developers of the BOOST and MTL4 libraries, who make programming in C++ such a pleasant experience.

The people who have developed discrete exterior calculus, for opening up this fresh path of enquiry.

Rob Hagmeijer, for valuable discussions on mathematics.

MOTIVATION

My personal motivation comes from a love for computational physics in general. Within this field, computational fluid dynamics is an especially rich and fascinating subject, and I am glad to have made it into my study.

Besides a study, computational physics is also a hobby to me. While researching for one of my hobby projects, I encountered the recent work in discrete exterior calculus. Impressed with the simplifying and unifying view it offered on numerical simulation, I was interested to see how these concepts might be applied within a fluid dynamics context. Few but fruitful work had been done in this area.

These methods have been developed in the context of computer science and animation: with a goal of making things move, and where plausibility is the goal. Yet the mathematical theory developed there, should also be applicable within an engineering context.

My original goal was to combining an existing advection scheme, inspired by discrete exterior calculus, and combine it with another technique, to overcome the weakness in the former, such as to obtain a conceptually simple and computationally effective incompressible flow solver, meeting the needs of engineers.

However, the advection path has been abandoned, in favor of expanding on my findings concerning boundary conditions; a change of scope to depth. Instead of merely combining existing numerical schemes, I felt that I had stumbled upon a novel contribution, that I was more excited about than my previous endgoal.

STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This switch of goals has some consequences for the structure of this document. Only the theory required to develop the results associated with the new goal is treated in depth, and not the theory associated with the old goal. Nonetheless, the interesting findings and some preliminary results associated with the old goal are briefly covered.

GOALS

The goal of this thesis is twofold:

On the one hand, I would like to convey the ideas underlying discrete exterior calculus and ab-initio finitistic scientific computing in general; to show that these developments are relevant outside computer science and animation; to give a self-contained, ab-initio account of discrete calculus, accessible to a wide audience.

On the other hand, I wish to convey my own contributions to this body of theory, concerning boundary conditions from the perspective of discrete calculus, and its implications for solution methods.

SUMMARY:

Discrete exterior calculus provides a rigorous discrete analogue of continuum exterior calculus. In its simplest form, this is equivalent to first-order tensor calculus, or vector calculus.

Finding the most general form of boundary conditions permissible for a system of vector calculus equations is a nontrivial problem. The most general form of boundary conditions for the Stokes equation has only been discovered recently, by a complicated and lengthy derivation. In discrete exterior calculus, such results can be obtained in a unified and simplified manner.

The notion of Poincare duality is extended to bounded domains. The resulting topological structure is analyzed, and some properties are derived.

From the discrete calculus point of view, the topological boundary terms demand boundary variables, which break the symmetry inherent to the equations. Restoring the symmetry of the equations forces the inclusion of additional equations on the boundary.

Applied to the Laplace equation, this procedure recovers the Robin boundary condition. Applied to the Stokes equations, this procedure yields two boundary conditions, which are similarly in agreement with previous results from continuum calculus.

Some theoretical results concerning the well-posedness of these boundary conditions are derived. Of particular interest is the symmetric structure guaranteed by this derivation of boundary conditions, which facilitates the design of solution algorithms.

The resulting boundary stencil is implemented and tested numerically. A convergence analysis is performed, and it is shown that the order of convergence is not adversely affected by the boundary conditions thus imposed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. DISCRETE EXTERIOR CALCULUS

The subject of this thesis is discrete exterior calculus (DEC) in the context of computational fluid dynamics. In order to use a computer to compute solutions to any physical problem, including those of fluid mechanics, the relevant physics need to be described in a finite number of variables. The standard approach is to discretize a set of continuum equations, using for instance the finite element method. There is a large number of seemingly arbitrary choices to be made in such a discretization process, and there are many ways in which a discretization can fail to obey fundamentally important mathematical and physical invariants.

One of the aims of discrete calculus is to construct simulations out of discrete building blocks, which are by construction guaranteed to have desirable properties, such as exactly satisfying conservation laws. These demands translate mathematically into symmetries and other algebraic properties. Not only are they relevant in faithfully reproducing the physics, but also for enabling efficient solution of the discrete equations.

“Our vision of this theory is that it should proceed ab- initio, as a discrete theory that parallels the continuous one. General views of the subject area of DEC are common in the literature, but they usually stress the process of discretizing a continuous theory and the overall approach is tied to this goal. However, if one takes the point of view that the discrete theory can stand in its own right, then the range of application areas is naturally enriched and increases” [21]

This statement is made out of pragmatic considerations, and I fully agree with it. Discrete calculus is a rapidly developing field, that has already found applications within a wide range of disciplines, such as computational fluid dynamics, computational electro dynamics, computational general relativity, computational mechanics, and many other fields [10].

In my thesis, I will try to make explicit the view that the discrete theory can stand in its own right, presenting it without appeals to continuum mathematics, and without assuming a background in mathematics beyond the one I have received as a student.

1.2. FINITISM

Discrete mathematics, such as discrete exterior calculus, does, unlike a calculus constructed out of the infinitely divisible continuum of real numbers, not invoke a notion of infinity. This underlies the intuitive view it offers on concepts in calculus.

The concept of infinity had already been thoroughly discussed by Aristotle and his contemporaries, and the consensus was that it was a paradoxical notion.

An illustration of a paradox involving infinity is attributed to Galileo, concerning the relation between the natural numbers and their squares. Any natural number can be squared, which implies there

being an equal number of natural numbers as squares. Yet clearly, not every natural number is a square, which proves there are more natural numbers than squares.

Salviati: So far as I see we can only infer that the totality of all numbers is infinite, that the number of squares is infinite, and that the number of their roots is infinite; neither is the number of squares less than the totality of all the numbers, nor the latter greater than the former; and finally the attributes "equal," "greater," and "less," are not applicable to infinite, but only to finite, quantities. When therefore Simplicio introduces several lines of different lengths and asks me how it is possible that the longer ones do not contain more points than the shorter, I answer him that one line does not contain more or less or just as many points as another, but that each line contains an infinite number.

From: Two new sciences by Galileo Galilei

The question ‘are there more natural numbers than squares?’ has therefore two answers: yes and no. Which is a contradiction; a paradox.

The pioneering work of Galileo on gravity inspired Newton to formulate his theory of gravitation. He formulated his physical theory in terms of relations between rates of change of physical variables, which he called ‘fluxions’; a novel concept at the time.

Newton’s original works are rarely read by anyone, as his technique of doing calculations has the reputation of being laborious. He formulated his theory entirely in terms of geometric constructions. Kepler’s law; ‘A line joining a planet and the sun sweeps out equal areas during equal intervals of time.’ is a good example of such a statement. That is, a finite area and a finite amount of time. Such a statement has the same information-content as conservation of angular momentum: the one implies the other, and vice versa.

In the years after Newton’s publication, people found they could arrive at the same results as he did, by means of *algebraic geometry*: associating a continuum of real numbers with a geometric line, leading to a calculus of real variables; that which we today associate with the word ‘calculus’. Newton himself had strong opinions on the matter:

Newton preferred the geometry of the “ancients”, particularly Euclid and Appolonius, to the recently introduced algebra of Descartes, which played an essential role in fluxional equations. He found the geometrical method “much more elegant than that of Descartes . . . [who] attains the result by means of an algebraic calculus which, if one transcribed it in words (in accordance with the practice of the Ancients in their writings) is revealed to be boring and complicated to the point of provoking nausea, and not be understood.”

from: Great Physicists by William H. Cropper

This notion of associating real numbers with geometric space took a high flight in the years after Newton. All subsequent physics was formulated in this method of a calculus of real variables.

Just as counting to infinity raised logical concerns, so does the notion of infinite divisibility. The modern view on these issues is substantially different from the one adhered to by Newton and pre-Newtonian mathematicians. These changes were driven by a desire to rationalize calculus, given its

tremendous success. Many present day mathematicians feel that these problems have been resolved by founding mathematics in set theory. A prominent figure in the establishment of set theory was Cantor, who's theorems concerning the nature of infinity are especially controversial.

As Leopold Kronecker claimed: "I don't know what predominates in Cantor's theory - philosophy or theology, but I am sure that there is no mathematics there." Many mathematicians agreed with Kronecker that the completed infinite may be part of philosophy or theology, but that it has no proper place in mathematics.

...

Cantor's ideas ultimately were largely accepted, strongly supported by David Hilbert, amongst others. Although constructivists and the intuitionists developed their schools of mathematics as a reaction to Cantor's infinitary ideas, most mathematicians do not have qualms about Cantor's Theory. It would appear that Hilbert's prediction has proved mostly accurate: "No one will drive us from the paradise which Cantor created for us" (Hilbert, 1926). To which Wittgenstein replied "if one person can see it as a paradise of mathematicians, why should not another see it as a joke?" (RFM V. 7).

Wikipedia: controversy over Cantor's theory

Personally, I feel Kronecker, Aristotle and Newton are correct, but unfortunately, explaining why is outside the scope of this work. Whatever one may think of these logical controversies, it is generally recognized that infinitary mathematics can be non-intuitive, or even counter-intuitive, and requires a higher level of abstraction to work with than mathematics which can be formulated entirely in terms of concrete constructions.

1.3. FLUID DYNAMICS

The algebraic calculus of Descartes and Leibniz, with its infinite divisibility and infinitesimals such as $\frac{dy}{dx}$, are not essential to fluid mechanics: physical principles such as conservation of mass, and conservation of momentum are.

A proper discrete formulation of fluid flow, obeying a discrete equivalent of these physical principles, will converge to the continuum equations. However, it will not converge the corresponding physical experiment! The Navier-Stokes equations are recognized to be an approximation to a deeper underlying truth. Mesh refinement beyond the molecular scale will not do anything to improve a discretization, and if nonexistent submolecular dynamics are enabled by these refinements, will even diverge from the physics being modeled as the continuum limit is approached.

As for what approach to favor in computational fluid dynamics, where the end-goal is a countably finite set of equations, the relevant question is a weighting of pragmatic concerns. What works, and what does it cost, in terms of human and silicon resources? From this pragmatic perspective, I feel a strong case can be made for making as little use of infinitary mathematics as possible.

We tend to view discrete mathematics as a mere numerical approximation of a deeper truth, unfit for search of new physical insight, but this is largely a consequence of historical developments, rather than justifiable with any strong arguments.

1.4. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Partial differential equations describe conditions which any solution must satisfy, such as conservation laws. These conditions implicitly define a whole family of solutions. Specifying a unique solution out of all these possibilities, requires boundary conditions.

Historically, finding the boundary conditions permissible for a given problem, has proven to be highly nontrivial. For instance, the Laplace equation was formulated in the late 18th century, but Dirichlet, Neuman and Robin, the people associated with the boundary conditions on the Laplace equation, lived long after Laplace. The proof of well posedness of the Dirichlet boundary conditions was given by Hilbert, in the early 20th century. Such proofs concerning boundary conditions are generally long and complicated.

Even though in case of the Laplace equation the permissible boundary conditions can at least be relatively easily conjectured from physical intuition, this approach fails for more complicated set of equations. The Stokes equations are one of the simpler models of fluid flow, and they have been known since the first half of the 19th century. Yet even a conjecture for the most general form of boundary conditions does not seem to have been found until recently. The first proof (known to the author) of its most general form of boundary conditions was published in 2003 [7], more than a century and a half since the Stokes equations were formulated. This proof consists of dozen of pages of symbolic manipulation, far beyond my mathematical sophistication.

From the discrete perspective, we may arrive at the same conclusions concerning boundary conditions for the Laplace and Stokes equations, using only a handful of intuitively accessible, basic mathematical-physical principles.

2. DISCRETE TOPOLOGY

2.1. INTRODUCTION

Topology plays an important role in discrete exterior calculus, and the new results which will be presented, derived within this framework. The field of topology can be concisely defined as geometry, minus metric. To give some appreciation for these concepts, Einsteins theory of gravitation will be considered.

A crucial element of his theory is that the distance between points in space is not a static a-priori given. Space is not a static background on which physics unfolds, but it is an active participant itself. In this way, predictions can be made which qualitatively and quantitatively defy any Newtonian type of gravitational theory, such as the deflection of light by mass.

An Einsteinian conception of space opens the door for a universe which is unbounded, yet finite in size, like the surface of a sphere. A circle drawn on a curved surface like a sphere, does not have a ratio of circumference to diameter of π , and astronomical observations do indeed reveal that the universe has a slight positive curvature, whatever its exact shape may be.

This greatly upsets classical notions of geometry. Having found a path between two points you deem straight, no longer guarantees you have found the shortest path between these points, and a different observer may not even agree said path is straight.

Topology is what remains of geometry after having completely exhausted all skeptical doubts concerning distance and shape. Properties concerning distance and shape are called metric properties. A straight line from a to b of length one is a geometric object. A line from a to b is the corresponding topological object. What remains can be described as connectivity and orientation.

Figure 2.1:

A cup with one handle and a torus are called homeomorphic; from a topological perspective, they have the same shape, as a mere transformation of relative distances would transform the one into the other, and vice versa. changing a torus into a wineglass is impossible without making a cut; without changing its connectivity.

Splitting geometry into topology and metric may seem like an unnecessary complication for anyone but theoretical physicists, but it can offer a simplifying view for the computational physicist as well.

Thus, topology deals with properties of space, invariant under continuous deformation. By discrete topology, we mean topological spaces constructed from a finite, countable set of building blocks.

The Euler characteristic of polyhedra, is one of the earliest examples of a topological relation. If V , E and F denote the number of vertices, edges and faces of a polyhedron, respectively, then we can define the Euler characteristic as: $\chi \equiv F - E + V$

Figure 2.2

The five platonic solids

One can prove, that for the surface of any platonic solid, $\chi = 2$ is always true (Figure 2.2). This is a good example of a topological property. Regardless of the size or shape of such a solid, whether it is the size of an apple, or the size of the earth, or bent into some other shape, this relation will not change.

A cube has 6 faces, 12 edges and 8 vertices, and we see that $\chi = 2$ indeed holds. We can immediately see that this relation must hold true for a class of constructions much broader than the Platonic solids, since splitting one face of the cube in two with an edge, will add both one edge and one face, thus keeping the Euler characteristic constant.

2.2. EDGES

The simplest topological construct is a line segment, or edge. As far as topology is concerned, an edge is fully defined by the specification of a begin and end point.

Figure 2.3

Consider Figure 2.3. Given two vertices v_1 and v_2 , their location being immaterial, an edge e_1 can be defined as $e_1 = +v_2 - v_1$. The signs do not denote the numerical operation of vector subtraction, but they denote orientation. The statement $+v_2$ means e_1 is oriented towards v_2 . Conversely, $-v_1$ means the edge is oriented away from v_1 . Similarly, one might write $e_2 = +v_2 - v_1$, and $e_3 = +v_1 - v_2$. Further, $e_1 = e_2 = -e_3$; By negating an edge, i.e. changing its sign, a reversal of its orientation is meant.

Note that whenever a line is drawn, a shape of the line is implicitly asserted. In general, a topological structure can only be visualized by rendering one specific geometric shape. One and the same topological edge, defines an entire family of line segments, of all possible shapes. In general, when topological objects are drawn in a certain shape, it is not implied that they should have this particular shape.

2.3. INCIDENCE MATRIX

The relations between multiple such edges and vertices can be encoded in an incidence matrix. Given some arbitrary arrangement of edges as in Figure 2.4, the corresponding incidence matrix is given.

Figure 2.4

An arbitrary collection of vertices, edges and their incidence matrix T_0^1 . The indices denote the dimensionality of the primitives being related.

Every column in the incidence matrix corresponds to an edge. Since every edge is connected to two vertices, every column has two nonzero entries, of opposite sign. Every vertex can be connected to an arbitrary number of edges.

2.4. PRIMITIVES

An edge is called a 1-dimensional topological primitive, and a vertex a 0-dimensional primitive. Just as an edge can be formed by specifying its bounding points, this process can be extended to higher dimensional primitives. Topological primitives of any dimension can be defined, by specification of their *closed boundary*. A set of primitives is considered closed, if it does itself not have a boundary. The boundary of any primitive is always of one dimension lower than the primitive itself.

For instance, a 2-dimensional primitive, a face, can be defined by specifying the edges that form its boundary. These edges only induce a separation of space, if said boundary does not itself have a boundary.

Figure 2.5

A closed set of edges does not have a boundary. A set of edges that does have a boundary necessarily has a hole in it, and it fails to provide a separation of space: we cannot determine a point as being on one side of the loop of edges or the other.

Similarly, any closed set of faces can be employed to define a volume. A set of faces with an opening in it, cannot be used to define a volume. (Figure 2.5)

Further, we demand that such a closed loop of edges has a *continuous orientation*. By having a continuous orientation, the loop uniquely specifies the orientation of the face being defined.

There is an important distinction with algebraic geometry that should be emphasized. When speaking of an edge in discrete topology, this is not meant to imply 'an infinite collection of points'. An edge is a begin and end point, nothing more. The same holds for other primitives. They are not to be regarded as collections of points. A face does not have two bounding sides, nor does a line have a bounding cylinder. A boundary in this context does not mean 'the set of points arbitrarily close to the primitive'. No statements concerning distance have yet been made, and there are no points except for the vertices which have been defined. When we speak of the boundary of a primitive, we always mean a set of lower dimensional primitives.

Figure 2.6

Picture of a 2D manifold

The topological information associating faces and edges can be encoded in an incidence matrix in a way analogous to the relation between edges and vertices. Either a face and edge are not related, they are aligned, or they are anti-aligned.

Figure 2.7

T_0^1	e_1	e_2	e_3	e_4	e_5	e_6	e_7
v_1					+	+	-
v_2	+	+			-		
v_3		-	+				
v_4			-	+		-	
v_5	-			-			+

T_1^2	f_1	f_2	f_3
e_1		+	
e_2	-		
e_3	-		
e_4			-
e_5	-	+	
e_6	+		-
e_7		+	-

Incidence matrices belonging to figure 2.6 (zeros and ones have been omitted for clarity)

So, $T_0^1(v_2, e_1) = +1$ means that e_1 is bounded on one side by v_2 , and oriented towards it. Likewise, $T_1^2(e_5, f_1) = -1$ means that e_5 is a boundary of f_1 , and their orientation is anti-aligned.

Defining a face in terms of its relative orientation to a set of edges, implies an orientation on the face. If this face is to be well defined, this loop of edges should be closed. Moreover, the orientations

should agree: a conflicting prescription of alignments can be conceived of, but it does not specify a face with a well-defined orientation.

This method of defining a topological space can be extended to arbitrary dimension. The incidence matrices, taken together, fully define the topology of the manifold. The sets of all k -primitives in a manifold is referred to as Σ^k . Another term for such a discrete manifold is a *complex*. This information is schematically represented in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8

A complex is fully defined by sets of primitives Σ^k and the topological relations between them.

2.5. SIMPLICES

Primitives as defined in terms of a closed boundary are a very broad class of objects: without loss of generality, more restrictive properties can be imposed upon topological building blocks.

An often used and convenient definition is that of a simplex. An n -simplex is a topological primitive defined in terms of $n+1$ boundary elements.

For example, any edge is necessarily a 1-simplex, always having two vertices. Triangles are 2-simplices, having three edges, and tetrahedra are 3-simplices, since they can be defined in terms of four triangular faces. This more restrictive definition is a useful simplification for many calculations.

2.6. CELLS

Another useful but broader subclass of primitives is the cell. An n -cell can be defined as being mathematically an n -ball, and hence its boundary being an $(n-1)$ -sphere.

In terms of algebraic geometry, a 3-ball is the set of all points satisfying the inequality $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 \leq 1$. Its boundary is the 2-sphere, defined by the equality $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1$. By extension, a disc is a 2-ball, a circle a 1-sphere, and so on.

In terms of discrete topology, a space is a circle or 1-sphere when it has Euler characteristic 0. Any closed loop of edges should have an equal number of edges and vertices. A space is said to be topologically a 2-sphere when it has Euler characteristic 2. Thus, all platonic solids are spheres, topologically speaking. More generally, any space that can be mapped onto a simplex is a ball: this definition extends more easily to higher dimensions, but is not necessary for the present work.

Figure 2.9

Different definitions in use.

Thus, all simplices are cells, and all cells are primitives: these relations are expressed in figure 2.9.

A discrete manifold consisting of only simplices is referred to as a simplicial complex, and one consisting of cells is referred to as a cell complex.

The aim of this definition, is to allow for constructions such as squares, hexagons and cubes, which are not simplices, but to exclude some pathologies allowed by the definition of a primitive, in terms of oriented boundary alone, as illustrated in figure 2.10..

Figure 2.10

The same topological space, both consisting of one face and six vertices, yet the number of edges is six and seven respectively. Under a broad definition of a primitive, a 'topological invariant' like the Euler characteristic, is neither invariant, nor characteristic.

Further, the definition of a cell should include a rejection of primitives connected with themselves.

Figure 2.11

The figure on the left, although a common type of construction in algebraic topology, cannot be represented in terms of incidence matrices. We can exclude such pathological constructions, without loss of generality; The same space is easily constructed out of balls not connected to themselves, as shown on the right.

2.7. ORIENTABILITY

Non-orientable manifolds are deemed a valid object of study in pure mathematics, but for physical purposes, they will be excluded. If we were to interpret a non-orientable space in physical terms: traversing a non-orientable universe would have you come back in reverse orientation; with your body mirrored once; your left and right hand reversed. Non-orientable spaces are incompatible with the aim of deriving a calculus. Formulating a Laplace equation over a non-orientable domain is not even possible.

Figure 2.12

A Möbius strip is an example of a non-orientable surface. It is not a ring with only one surface: a ring has only one orientable surface, topologically speaking. A Möbius strip has none.

A non-orientable space such as in Figure 2.12 contains at least one edge with identical orientation to both its incident faces. Such a discontinuity in orientation is excluded from consideration, and only orientable spaces will be considered.

2.8. CHAINS

Subdomains of a manifold can be expressed in terms of linear combinations of cells. Essentially, a vector of coefficients over the linear space spanned by a set of cells.

Subsets of Σ^k can be described by linear combinations of the elements in Σ^k . If σ_i is a cells in Σ^k , this can be written as:

$$c^k = \sum_{i \in \Sigma^k} c_i \sigma_i \quad (2.1)$$

We refer to c^k as a chain in the linear space spanned by Σ^k , which is therefore a vector with three possible values, -1,0 and +1.

Taking the complex from figure 2.5 as an example, the chain $c^2 = [1 \ 1 \ 0]$ on Σ^2 reads simply as $f_1 + f_2$, the geometric sum, or union of these two faces.

Figure 2.13

Graphical depiction of c^2 , a subdomain of the manifold in figure 2.6

This abstraction is introduced in order to be able to interpret the topology matrix as a linear operator. Since T_1^2 has a number of columns equal to the cardinality of Σ^2 , T_1^2 can be right-multiplied with c^2 .

Performing this computation, $c^1 = T_1^2 c^2$ a vector $c^1 = [+1 \ -1 \ -1 \ 0 \ 0 \ +1 \ +1]$ is obtained, which has the same cardinality as Σ^1 . We can interpret this result as a chain c^1 on Σ^1 , that is, a linear combination of the edges in the manifold. Drawing this set of edges as in Figure 2.13, we see that by this action of

the topology matrix, the boundary of the subdomain described by c^2 is obtained. Note that the orientation of c^1 and c^2 agree, and that the interior edge has cancelled.

Figure 2.14

c^1 , the oriented boundary of c^2

2.9. THE BOUNDARY OPERATOR

Hence, the action of right-multiplying with the topology matrix is called the boundary operator, ∂ .

This process can be extended to any topology matrix, including T_0^1 : by right-multiplying T_0^1 with c^1 , a chain c^0 on Σ^0 is obtained,. Performing this computation, we see that the result is the zero vector.

This is not a coincidence, but a direct consequence of the requirement that any primitive is defined in terms of a closed boundary. The boundary of any (sub)manifold is a closed manifold, and the boundary of a closed manifold does by definition, not exist.

Hence, this is a universal property of the boundary operator. We can conclude that $\partial\partial = \emptyset$ for any well defined manifold. Or in terms of the topology matrices, $T_0^1 T_1^2 = 0$: multiplying any two consecutive topology matrices must yield the zero matrix. The sequence of incidence matrices is said to be *exact*.

Summarizing, every set of simplices can be used as the basis of a linear space, and every topology matrix defines an operator between these spaces. These relations are summarized in figure 2.15.

Figure 2.15

Abstract representation of a 2D manifold and its boundary operators

2.10. POINCARÉ DUALITY

With every manifold, a dual manifold can be associated, called its Poincaré dual.

The notion of topological duality is closely related to geometric dualities, such as the Voronoi dual. All Platonic solids come in primal-dual pairs. The icosahedron and dodecahedron are an example of such a primal-dual pair.

Figure 2.16

*Example of a 2d manifold embedded in a 3d space
 blue: icosahedron on the surface of a sphere
 red: its geometric dual, the dodecahedron*

The essential feature of topological duality is the establishment of a one-to-one correspondence between pairs of cells. Given a primal complex of dimension n , a dual complex can be constructed by associating with each primal (k) -cell a dual $(n-k)$ - cell.

For example: with every face of the dodecahedron, a vertex of the icosahedrons is associated, and so forth. An icosahedron has 20 faces, 30 edges and 12 vertices, while the dodecahedron has 12 faces, 30 edges, and 20 vertices.

In the context of a primal-dual complex, a more specific notation is introduced: P_k denotes the set of primal k - cells, and P_k^{k+1} the topological relations between sets of cells

The topological dual does not introduce any truly new topology, as every dual cell is directly associated with a primal cell. There is no freedom in choosing the topological relations between dual cells.

This is elegantly reflected in the fact that the incidence matrices of the dual can be obtained by transposing the primal incidence matrices.

Thus for a 2D manifold this would yield $D_1^2 = (P_0^1)^T$, and $D_0^1 = (P_1^2)^T$, or in general

$$D_k^{k+1} = (P_{n-(k+1)}^{n-k})^T \tag{2.2}$$

Figure 2.17

Diagram of a primal-dual complex pair. There exists a one-to-one relation between primal and dual primitives, indicated with vertical lines

The dual is itself a well-defined complex, for which the definition of the boundary operator applies. These relations are summarized in figure 2.17. In the context of orientability, we note that the primal complex being orientable, corresponds to the dual complex having only edges with a distinct begin and endpoint. In a 2D manifold, every edge has two incident faces. If the manifold is oriented, then it must have both one aligned and one anti-aligned incident face. The incident primitives of the primal edge correspond to the bounding primitives of the dual mesh, hence the dual edge is has both one vertex it is aligned with, and one it is anti-aligned with: a begin and end point.

Conversely, demanding that all primal edges have a distinct begin and endpoint, implies that that dual complex is orientable. This further emphasizes the importance of orientability.

This exposition concerning topology is a summary of the relevant facts collected from various references [2], [3], [4], [10].

This example is intentionally given in the context of a closed manifold, such as the surface of an icosahedron. In context of manifolds having a boundary, Poincare duality does not apply. In trying to apply Poincare duality to a bounded domain, complications arise.

2.11. BOUNDED DOMAINS

The defining characteristic of the boundary of a complex are the $n-1$ cells incident to only one n -cell. For $n = 2$, as in figure 2.18, this means edges with only one incident face. Under duality, these correspond to dual edges bounded by only one dual vertex. That is, they are ill-defined; they fail to meet the definition of a primitive. Straightforward application of the notion of Poincare duality to bounded domains is not possible.

Not only the dual boundary edges are ill defined, but neither do the dual faces corresponding to primal boundary vertices have a closed boundary, nor any higher dimensional generalizations.

Figure 2.18

Dual manifold obtained by straightforward application of duality. Continuous edges form the primal, dotted lines the dual. The dual cells corresponding to primal boundary cells are ill-defined. For instance, some edges only have one bounding point.

Demanding all dual cells are well defined, that is, they have a complete, closed boundary, and doing so by adding a minimum number of cells, yields unambiguous rules for the completion of the dual complex.

Figure 2.19

The dual complex obtained by applying Poincare duality to a bounded primal complex needs an additional set of cells to fix any resultant cells which are not closed. This process is visualized in figure 2.19. We can capture this logic by the following formal yet concise statement:

If for a closed manifold we state

$$D = * P \tag{2.3}$$

where P and D denote the primal and corresponding dual manifold, and the $*$ symbol denotes their duality relation, then for a bounded manifold we can state:

$$D = * P \cup * \partial P \tag{2.4}$$

That is, the set of all dual topological cells can be constructed as the union of the dual of all primal cells and the dual of all cells in the boundary of the primal mesh, as expressed diagrammatically in figure 2.20.

The boundary of the primal mesh is itself a closed $n-1$ manifold. By definition, the boundary does itself not have a boundary, so this construction of a well-defined dual does not imply a recursion.

Similar observations have been made in [11], in context of the specification of initial values on space-time manifolds.

Figure 2.20

Diagram capturing primal-dual relations. The diagonals represent boundary contributions to the set of dual cells. A dual vertex is added for every primal boundary edge, and a dual edge is added for every primal boundary vertex. This construction is similarly valid for higher dimensions

Note that in figure 2.19, the dual of the primal boundary strictly follows the primal boundary itself. From the topological point of view, the shape of cells is immaterial by definition, thus we are free to demand it be so.

Yet we do not only concern ourselves with topology. Typically, we wish to deduce a metric from an embedding space. This is not a matter of topology, but of geometry. Likewise, visualization of data is not merely a matter of topology: in order to even draw such a figure, one has to assume a shape.

From an implementational point of view, it is appealing to introduce additional primitives beyond those mentioned so far, in order to have the domain of the dual mesh conform to the primal, purely in terms of straight line segments. For instance, a dual vertex could be inserted at every primal boundary vertex, thus splitting the dual boundary edges. As will become apparent in later sections; from the discrete calculus point of view, introducing such topologically redundant cells corresponds to introducing additional variables without introducing equations to match them. Any implementation of these concepts is well advised to maintain a clear distinction between topological and metric aspects.

2.12. LINEAR ALGEBRAIC OBSERVATIONS

Extending the dual topology as described, requires augmentations to the incidence matrix. To this end, some additional structure will be imposed on the topology matrices.

For any n -dimensional manifold, the set of primal topological cells can be split into two categories, belonging to either the interior or the boundary of the domain.

For n - cells, this distinction is meaningless. For instance, faces in a two dimension domain cannot meaningfully be considered to be part of the boundary, therefore, they are all categorized as interior cells.

The defining characteristic of an (n-1) boundary cell is it having only one incident n- cell. In a 2D manifold, the edges incident to only one face are part of the boundary. All other edges should have two incident faces.

The interior-boundary distinction for all lower-order elements can be stated inductively: they are a boundary cell, when they have at least one incident boundary cell. An example of such a splitting is given in figure 2.21.

Figure 2.21

2D Primal cell complex, continuous edges are boundary edges, dotted edges interior edges. Solid vertices are boundary vertices, the open vertex an interior vertex.

By grouping cells into boundary and interior sets, a 2x2 block structure is imposed on the primal topology matrices. Interior cells are denoted with a subscript i, cells on the primal boundary are denoted with a subscript p.

Starting with the P_1^2 matrix:

$$P_1^2 = \begin{matrix} & f_i & f_p \\ e_i & x & \cdot \\ e_p & U & \cdot \end{matrix} \tag{2.5}$$

The lower-left block U is a non-square unitary matrix: it has exactly one non-zero entry in every row (Figure 2.22), by virtue of it consisting of boundary edges, which have only one incident face by definition. If both the domain and its boundary are continuously oriented, all these entries will have the same sign.

Figure 2.22

	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4
e_1	+1			
e_2	+1			
e_3		+1		
e_4		+1		
e_5			+1	
e_6			+1	
e_7				+1
e_8				+1

One possible realization of the $P_1^2[e_p, f_i]$ term for the manifold in figure 2.20. Every boundary edge has by definition one incident face. In this particular example, every face has two incident boundary edges, but in general, this can be any number, including zero.

The rightmost block-column of the P_1^2 matrix has zero columns in it: there are no boundary faces. This is denoted with dots in the corresponding entries.

The upper-left most block has some non-zero structure which is of no further concern.

The P_0^1 matrix has one zero block: there can be no relation between a boundary edge and an interior vertex, as the boundary vertices as defined as being only those vertices which are incident to boundary edges.

$$P_0^1 = \begin{matrix} & e_i & e_p \\ v_i & x & 0 \\ & v_p & x & B_0^1 \end{matrix} \quad (2.6)$$

The lower right block consists of topological relations purely between boundary edges and boundary vertices. It describes the closed 1-dimensional manifold of the primal boundary, and it is assigned the label B_0^1

The D_0^1 matrix is the P_1^2 matrix transposed, but augmented with an additional row and column block, subscripted by a d, to accommodate the to-be-determined topological information of the dual boundary. Note that we are considering dual cells now, denoted by an apostrophe. The expression ' e_p ' does not denote primal edges, but reads as 'the dual edges corresponding to primal boundary edges'.

$$D_0^1 = (P_1^2)^T \cup \dots = \begin{array}{cccc} & 'e_i & 'e_p & 'e_d \\ 'v_i & x & U^T & 0 \\ 'v_p & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 'v_d & 0 & \pm I & (B_0^1)^T \end{array} \quad (2.7)$$

The dual intra-boundary topological structure $D_0^1 [v_d, e_d]$ is simply the primal intra-boundary topology B_0^1 transposed. That is, we apply Poincare duality to the closed sub manifold of the boundary.

The $[v_d, e_p]$ block must be square, since exactly one dual boundary vertex is introduced for every edge on the primal boundary. It is set such as to close the otherwise ill-defined dual edges corresponding to primal boundary edges ($'e_p$). As noted before, each column in this matrix has only one non-zero entry, these entries being of the same sign.

Formally, $\text{diag}(D_0^1 [v_d, 'e_p]) = -\text{rowsum}(D_0^1 [v_i, 'e_p])$, or $D_0^1 [v_d, 'e_p]_{jj} = -\sum_i D_0^1 [v_i, 'e_p]_{ij}$. It is not necessarily an identity matrix, but it should be one, up to sign and enumeration conventions.

That is, $D_0^1 [v_d, e_p]^T D_0^1 [v_d, e_p] = I$ should be true under all circumstances.

The D_1^2 matrix follows the same logic, of transpose plus augmentation, yet the situation is somewhat different.

$$D_1^2 = (P_0^1)^T \cup \dots = \begin{array}{cccc} & 'f_i & 'f_p & 'f_d \\ 'e_i & x & x & \cdot \\ 'e_p & 0 & (B_0^1)^T & \cdot \\ 'e_d & 0 & \pm I & \cdot \end{array} \quad (2.8)$$

The last column is empty: the process of closing the boundary does not add any additional dual faces. The lower-left block is zero, since dual boundary edges are never incident to dual faces corresponding to primal interior vertices.

Qualitatively, the structure of $D_1^2 [e_d, f_p]$ is obvious: it should be square unitary matrix, since every dual boundary edge should be connected to exactly one dual face. The correct signs and enumerations can be deduced by the following argument: if these dual topology matrices are to be well-formed, the exact sequence property, $D_0^1 D_1^2 = 0$ should hold. The only nontrivial block in this zero right-hand side comes from substituting the $D_1^2 [f_p]$ column in the $D_0^1 [v_d]$ row.

Writing out this product, we obtain

$$(D_0^1 [v_d, 'e_p])B_0^1 + B_0^1(D_1^2 [e_d, 'f_p]) = 0 \quad (2.9)$$

By demanding continuous orientation of the primal manifold, the $D_0^1 [v_d, 'e_p]$ term it is not just a unitary matrix, but a (possibly negated) identity matrix, who's multiplication fully commutes with any boundary topology term, regardless of its structure.

Hence,

$$D_0^1 [{}'v_d, {}'e_p] = -D_1^2 [{}'e_d, {}'f_p] \quad (2.10)$$

Thus if $D_0^1 [{}'v_d, {}'e_p] = I$, then $D_1^2 [{}'e_d, {}'f_p] = -I$: they are both identity matrices, of alternating sign.

In conclusion, we note that by definition, the [d,p] terms are always square unitary matrices, and it should always be possible to express these terms as identity matrices of alternating sign, by demanding continuous orientation of the primal complex.

3. DISCRETE CALCULUS

3.1. DISCRETE DIFFERENTIAL FORMS

An essential difference between discrete calculus and algebraic calculus is the representation of data. In real analysis, data is expressed in terms of functions of real variables, i.e. $u(x, y)$, and it is a habit that tends to carry over to discretized formulations, i.e. $u(x_i, y_j)$.

In discrete calculus, a different approach is taken. The state variables are not associated with a Cartesian coordinate, but they are associated with the primitives of the underlying manifold. We can thus say that a function has some value at a vertex, and another value at another vertex, but nowhere in the calculations will the position of these vertices relative to a background space take on any significance.

In analogy with the definition of a chain over a set of primitives, we can define a so called differential form over a set of primitives. Mathematically, they are identical entities: finite-dimensional vectors in the linear space spanned by the set of primitives. A chain is physically interpreted as a linear combination of primitives, hence having only coefficients $-1, 0$ or $+1$, and thus describing a subdomain of the manifold. Differential forms have no such restriction: they associate with every primitive an arbitrary number. The interpretation of a differential form is as describing a field quantity over the manifold.

Differential forms can be defined over the linear space spanned by any set of primitives, the dimensionality of the primitives being denoted by a subscript. Thus ω_0 would describe a value associated with every vertex. Often, this subscript is omitted if it is obvious from the context. In the limit to infinite refinement, we make a scalar statement about a field in every conceivable point in space. Thus, a 0-form can be regarded as the discrete analog of a scalar field.

By contrast, a 1-form does not correspond to a scalar field. Its interpretation is a scalar value being associated with every edge in the manifold. A point does not have an intrinsic sense of orientation, yet an edge does. It can be interpreted as the coordinate-free discrete representation of a vector field. Thus, we do not describe a vector field in terms of components along coordinate axes, but the intrinsic orientation of the edges, combined with the amount of flux along that edge, is used to represent a directional field quantity.

We recall the definition of the integral of tangent flux $\int_L (\vec{F} \cdot \vec{t}) dL$ and normal flux $\iint_S (\vec{F} \cdot \vec{n}) dS$ from vector calculus, and we see that they can indeed be regarded as number associated with an underlying domain, the line L and surface S respectively.

In three dimensions, the differential form defined on any set of primitives has a unique interpretation. 0-forms and 3-forms correspond to scalar fields. 1-forms correspond to tangent fluxes, and 2-forms to normal fluxes. These 2-forms, or numbers on faces, also describe a directional field quantity, since a face also has an intrinsic sense of orientation. A 2-form assigns to every face in the manifold a number corresponding to the flux through that face.

Figure 3.1

Different fields that can be formulated over a 3D manifold in discrete calculus

In general, on an n-d manifold, 0-forms and n-forms offer a representation of scalar fields, and 1-forms and n-1-forms offer a representation of fields with an intrinsic sense of orientation, or vector fields. For 1,2 and 3 dimensions, all possible forms have a simple interpretation, but the concept extends meaningfully to higher dimensions as well. For instance, extending the manifold to cover a time-direction straightforwardly leads to a class of mimetic time-discretized schemes [11].

Locating field variables in differential forms is a restriction as compared to the freedom of choice offered by a finite element method, for instance. Within this framework, vector fields are represented as forms, and this framework does not permit a collocated grid. This seems like a limiting restriction, but within these constraints many physical problems can be fully expressed. It is precisely this constraint which leads to desirable mathematical-physical properties.

As a general mathematical-physical principle, physically meaningful quantities must be background-independent. A vector field satisfies these properties: we may rotate its basis, but this does not change the essence of the vector field. A single component of a vector field in isolation on the other hand, has no such rotation invariance, and cannot be a meaningful physical quantity. The 2D vorticity $\frac{du}{dy} - \frac{dv}{dx}$ is a valid field, but either of these components taken in isolation as a scalar field, is not. By directly relating variables to the underlying geometry, rather than some global coordinate system, this constraint is naturally enforced. The only fields permitted are physically meaningful fields.

It can at various times be useful to convert between a differential form and vector field representation and vice versa, e.g. for visualization. We might for instance try to find a vector at some vertex, that matches the fluxes in its incident edges. These conversion operators are called sharp and flat respectively: in continuum exterior calculus, these operations are each other's exact inverses, but in DEC such a conversion can never be exact [3]. Merely by consideration of the degrees

of freedom, we can see that this mapping cannot be one-to-one. A vector defined at each vertex, having a number of components equal to the dimension, has a different number of degrees of freedom than a scalar defined at every edge. A collocated grid and a staggered grid are not interchangeable without loss of information.

3.2. DISCRETE EXTERIOR DERIVATIVE

The linear-algebraic representation of forms allows for a direct definition of the fundamental operation in discrete exterior calculus: the discrete exterior derivative.

In chapter 2.7, the boundary operator was defined as right-multiplication by the appropriate incidence matrix. The discrete exterior derivative is defined as the transpose of the boundary operator, or given the stated conventions, left-multiplication with the appropriate incidence matrix.

If the boundary ∂ of a chain c^{k+1} is given by:

$$c^k = \partial c^{k+1} \quad (3.1)$$

Then the 'exterior derivative' d of the differential form ω^k can be found as:

$$\omega^{k+1} = d\omega^k \quad (3.2)$$

Where the exterior derivative is the transpose of the boundary operator:

$$d = \partial^T \quad (3.3)$$

This relation between the boundary operator and the exterior derivative is also referred to as the generalized Stokes theorem. The generalized Stokes theorem holds true for any k . As k is varied, relations between forms of different degree are obtained, and different differential operators are generated.

Figure 3.2

Diagram displaying the relation between the boundary operator and the exterior derivative

Like the boundary operator, the exterior derivative is typically used as a context-dependent symbol. Applying the exterior derivative to a 0-form is not the same operation as applying it to a 1-form, but if no further qualification is provided, the specific operator should be deducible from the context.

Since $\partial\partial = 0$, this implies $dd = 0$. The boundary of a boundary does not exist, regardless of the domain considered, and thus, the exterior derivative of the exterior derivative is zero, regardless of what differential form is supplied as input. Like the boundary operators, the exterior derivatives form an exact sequence. If $d\omega = 0$, ω is called a closed form, in analogy with a closed chain.

The discrete exterior derivative is defined for both the primal and dual complex. The dual exterior derivative is denoted with the symbol δ . In order to obtain agreement between the most important sign conventions in vector and exterior calculus, it is convenient to negate the definition of the dual exterior derivative, thus $\delta = -d^T$. These relations are summarized in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3

2D manifold and all the operators defined thus far

3.3. RELATION TO VECTOR CALCULUS

The elements of discrete calculus presented thus far provide a discrete analog of fundamental operations in vector calculus. The relation with continuum calculus is the subject of ongoing research, see [20]

To investigate the link between discrete calculus and vector calculus, three-dimensional manifolds will be considered first.

3.3.1. THE FUNDAMENTAL THEOREM OF CALCULUS

The Fundamental theorem of calculus (FTC) on the real line reads:

$$\int_a^b \frac{dF}{dx} dx = F(b) - F(a) \quad (3.4)$$

Or its generalization to higher dimensions:

$$\int_L (\text{grad}(F) \cdot \vec{t}) dL = F(b) - F(a) \quad (3.5)$$

Where $\partial L = [a, b]$

The FTC is an implicit definition of the derivative: shrinking the interval $[a, b]$ to zero, gives a definite statement concerning the nature of the derivative. We see this reflected in the higher dimensional analog, which allows for an intuitive interpretation in terms of a path over a hilltop: slope is that which, integrated between the endpoints of a line, is equal to the difference between endpoints.

The exterior derivative of a 0-form yields a 1-form, or $\omega^1 = d\omega^0$. Interpreting this product, we see that the exterior derivative corresponds to a topology matrix between edges and vertices. By action of this multiplication, to every edge a value is assigned equal to the difference between the values on the vertices of its endpoints. Every edge has one begin and one end point, and their corresponding -1 and +1 coefficients are multiplied with the 0-form and summed.

Thus, if we interpret 1-forms as integrals of tangent flux over the corresponding edge, the exterior derivative on 0-forms is an *exact* discrete analog of the fundamental theorem of calculus.

3.3.2. STOKES THEOREM

The curl is a differential operator which obeys Stokes theorem:

$$\iint_S (\text{curl}(\vec{F}) \cdot \vec{n}) dS = \oint_{\partial S} (\vec{F} \cdot \vec{t}) dL \quad (3.6)$$

We may take two views of such a theorem: as a relation one might prove from a definition of the curl operator in terms of partial derivatives in some coordinate system, or as the defining relation of curl in arbitrary coordinate systems.

Like the FTC, this is a relation between the integral of some function over a domain, and the integral (sum) of some function over the boundary of that domain. On the left hand side, we see a surface integral of normal flux, on the right-hand size, a line integral of tangent flux.

Given a 1-form, application of the exterior derivative to it, yields a 2-form, $\omega^2 = d\omega^1$. The interpretation of this product is to set the value on every face in the 2-form equal to the sum of the

tangent fluxes around it. If we interpret the 2-form as the integral of normal flux over a face, then the exterior derivative between 2-forms and 1-forms is an *exact* discrete analog of the curl operator.

3.3.3. GAUSS' DIVERGENCE THEOREM

Gauss' divergence theorem states:

$$\iiint_V \operatorname{div}(\vec{F}) dV = \iint_{\partial V} (\vec{F} \cdot \vec{n}) dS \quad (3.7)$$

Like the Stokes theorem or the fundamental theorem of calculus, we may think of it as the defining relation of divergence. 'the total divergence within a volume, is that which leaves through its boundary'.

The interpretation of the discrete exterior derivative over 2-forms is a summation of normal fluxes over the boundary. Therefore, it is an exact discrete analog of the divergence operator.

Even though the fundamental theorem of calculus has a certain intuitive appeal (the net amount of descent is only a function of the begin and endpoint, not of the path between them), the proof that the flux along a boundary equals the normal flux of vorticity over any surface spanned by that boundary, has no such intuitive appeal.

The validity of such theorems is immediately obvious in discrete calculus, as the exterior derivative directly defines these relations. They are truths by definition. Normal flux is that, which summed over a boundary equals divergence. The shape of this volume in this statement, is completely immaterial. Thus, as can be seen from the definition in terms of the boundary operator, the exterior derivative is purely a matter of topology, and not of metric.

These interpretations in analogy with vector calculus are summarized in figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4

We see from this interpretation that discrete exterior calculus exactly satisfies fundamental vector relations such as $\nabla \times \nabla = 0$ and $\nabla \cdot \nabla \times = 0$: a gradient field has zero curl, and the curl of a field has zero divergence. This follows directly from the requirement that all boundaries are closed.

A discretization which does not respect these identities, such as offered by a straightforward collocated vector grid, has the geometric interpretation of implying primitives having boundaries which are not closed, which is impossible. Respecting these algebraic properties on the discrete level is an ingredient to the proof of well-posedness and absence of spurious modes one can give for equations formulated in this framework [3]. This is what makes all discrete equations derived within this framework *mimetic* to the continuum equations.

Further, we note that there exist an exact symmetry between primal-dual pairs of differential operators. Every operator is match by another which equals its transpose.

3.3.4. 2D MANIFOLDS

The 2-dimensional manifold introduces a subtlety: values associated with edges can be interpreted both as tangent fluxes and normal fluxes, and defining them introduces a seemingly arbitrary choice. There are reasons to choose them as defined in figure 3.5, which will become apparent. This choice of interpretations will force our interpretation of the exterior derivative, which proceeds analogous to the 3D case, except now we obtain a discrete analog to Green's theorem.

Figure 3.5

Note that in algebraic calculus, a 3D space has only one curl operator; mapping vector fields to vector fields, but a 2D space has two; one that maps a vector field to a scalar field, for instance, velocity to vorticity, and one that maps a scalar field to a vector field, for instance, a stream function to velocity.

Exterior calculus offers a beautiful unification of all these seemingly fundamentally different vector operations, and exposes them as essentially one and the same operator: the adjoint of the boundary operator. In algebraic exterior calculus, this relation is very abstract, but in the discrete setting, it makes vector calculus very intuitively accessible.

3.4. METRIC

“The introduction of numbers as coordinates. . . is an act of violence. . . ”

Hermann Weyl

From a mathematical point of view, the metric is a function that assigns a notion of distance to a manifold. A standard Euclidian space has an implicit trivial unit metric: the points $x = 1$ and $x = 2$ are a distance $2 - 1 = 1$ apart.

Given two points on the surface of a sphere, their distance within the surface cannot be found by applying Pythagoras to their coordinates. In such a situation, the metric will be some nontrivial function of real variables. In an Euclidian space the notion of distance is implied by Pythagoras' theorem, but in more abstract mathematical spaces such as polar coordinates, the distance between points is entirely meaningless without a metric. A metric is what gives meaning to measurements such as distance and area.

In algebraic geometry, a metric takes the form of a function between real variables: a transformation from some background space to a physical space. Yet in general, there need not be a background space. How does one define distance without an underlying coordinate system? In a discrete setting, we can directly assign it to the underlying topology. If we say that a line has length one, we say that the distance between its endpoints is one.

In discrete calculus, the metric on a manifold will take a form of one number assigned to every primitive σ^k , which is called its 'generalized volume', or $|\sigma^k|$. The generalized volume of a line is its length, the generalized volume of a face is its area, and so on. The generalized volume of vertices is always one.

3.4.1. EUCLIDIAN METRIC

Although strictly speaking, this is not a necessity, one typically works by assuming an algebraic embedding space as a background. Every vertex is assigned a position in some coordinate space.

Thus, we may try to make our discrete metric conform to the Euclidian background. This requires us to make further assumptions on the topological manifold. Piecewise linearity of the manifold is a convenient though not necessary choice. Assuming piecewise linearity, edge-lengths are readily computed from vertex positions in the embedding space.

The area of an arbitrary polygon in the plane can be computed by application of Gauss' divergence theorem. One can choose some arbitrary divergent vector-valued function of divergence one. Thus, the integral of the divergence of this function over any face should equal its area, which in turn should equal the integral of normal flux over the boundary. The integral of normal flux over the boundary is trivially computed for any edge, thus the area of any polygon can be computed by summing these values.

3.4.2. SPHERICAL METRIC

There is no need to require straightness of lines, or flatness of faces. If we wish for a spherical topology to conform to the metric of a sphere, the length of edges can be computed by proportionality to the angle between the vectors from the origin to two points on the sphere,

Calculating the area of a spherical polygon on a sphere of radius R proceeds as follows:

From geometric constructions, one can prove that the area of a spherical triangle must relate to its inscribed angles as $A = R^2(\alpha + \beta + \gamma - \pi)$, where α, β, γ denote the inscribed angles at the vertices in radians. This can be generalized to arbitrary polygons as $A = R^2(\theta - (n - 2)\pi)$, with n the number of vertices, and θ the sum of their inscribed angles.

3.4.3 GEOMETRIC DUALITY

By Poincare duality, we associate with every primal n -primitive a dual 0 -primitive, or dual vertex. Yet the location of this vertex with respect to the n -primitive has so far been left completely unspecified.

There are two predominant forms of geometric duality in use: circumcentric duality, and barycentric duality. The circumcentric dual is otherwise known as the Voronoi dual.

Barycentric duality locates the dual vertices in the barycenter, or center of mass, of their associated primal n -primitives. This has the advantage of the center of mass being guaranteed to lie within the primitive, on the condition that the primitive is convex.

Circumcentric duality locates the dual vertices in the circumcenter of the vertices of the n -cell. The circumcenter is the location that has equal distance to all vertices of the cell. It is not well-defined for arbitrary cells, but it is well defined for simplices or regular polyhedrons such as squares and hexagons. A simplex is guaranteed to have a circumcenter, but the circumcenter is not guaranteed to lie within the simplex.

Such situations have adverse consequences for subsequent calculations, thus the circumcentric dual poses stricter constraints on the aspect ratio of a mesh. An advantage of the voronoi dual is that it guarantees the geometric orthogonality of primal-dual pairs of cells. in a 2D manifold, primal edges will be orthogonal to dual edges, and in a 3D manifold, primal edges will be orthogonal to dual faces, and vice versa.

Figure 3.6

The circumcenters of two triangles, with a primal and associated dual edge in bold. The circumcentric construction guarantees orthogonality of all edges. (or any higher-dimensional primal-dual pair)

3.4.4. HODGE STAR OPERATOR

The Hodge star operator provides a mapping between a primal and dual representation of forms. By definition of the dual mesh, every primal k -primitive is matched by a dual $n-k$ -primitive.

For instance, for every primal vertex, there exists a corresponding dual n -primitive. Both can serve as a basis for a scalar field, and the Hodge star operator provides a mapping between these dual representations. Discrete vector fields do similarly come in primal-dual pairs which we may relate to each other.

Given a primal form ω^k on a primal cell σ^k , and its corresponding dual form $'\omega^{n-k}$ on a dual cell $'\sigma^{n-k}$, they can be related by the following transformation:

$$\frac{\omega^k}{|\sigma^k|} = \frac{'\omega^{n-k}}{|'\sigma^{n-k}|} \quad (3.8)$$

Where we recall that $|\sigma^k|$ means the 'generalized volume' of the cell σ^k . This equation can thus be interpreted as the cell-averaged values of corresponding primal and dual forms being equated.

A transformation between n -forms and 0 -forms corresponds to a straightforward cell-averaging: the value on the n -primitive is divided by its 'generalized volume', and the value on the 0 -form is divided by one: it is left unchanged.

In terms of a physical interpretation, we may think of it as a mapping between the total amount of mass in a cell, and the corresponding density in a related point.

This relation makes sense for direction vector-type quantities as well. Given an edge in a 2D manifold, or a face in a 3D manifold, their Voronoi dual is both an edge orthogonal to the primal. It

can be interpreted as the associated normal direction. Dividing the integral of tangent flux by length gives a quantity in vectorial dimensions, and so does dividing the integral of normal flux by its corresponding generalized volume. The sign convention for the normal (left-handed or right-handed) is implied by the arbitrary choices of orientation in the formulation of the complex.

Figure 3.7

A primal 1-simplex σ^1 and its dual 1-simplex $'\sigma^1$: if we choose the position of the dual vertices according to the Voronoi diagram, they will be orthogonal by construction.

Thus, a transformation between forms ω^k on P^k and their dual $'\omega^{n-k}$ on D^{n-k} can be defined as the diagonal matrix:

$$*_{ii} = \frac{|\sigma_i|}{|\sigma_i|} \tag{3.9}$$

Which is referred to as the Hodge star operator. Its inverse can be given explicitly as:

$$*^{-1}_{ii} = \frac{|\sigma_i|}{|\sigma_i|} \tag{3.10}$$

Thus, $'\omega^{n-k} = * \omega^k$ and $\omega^k = *^{-1} '\omega^{n-k}$

The inverse symbol is omitted if the type of transformation to apply is specified uniquely by the context. The relation between the operators discussed so far, is represented diagrammatically in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8

2D primal-dual manifold and its operators

The Hodge star operator is where discrete calculus deviates from the continuum theory: the differential operators and the metric can be interpreted as exact equivalents of the continuum theory, but the Hodge star can only agree with its continuum counterpart in the continuum limit.

It should be noted that the choice of the Hodge star is not unique. One might for instance construct mappings between primal and dual representations with a wider stencil, thus a non-diagonal matrix, and arrive at discrete equations with higher order convergence to the continuum. [12]

The key property of the Hodge star, however defined, is that it should be a square, positive definite matrix of full rank. This minimal set of properties is all that is required to guarantee well-posedness, independently of whether the suggested metric allows for an embedding.

3.5. FORMULATING OPERATORS

The discrete exterior derivative is a first-order differential operator. Systems of equations and higher-order operators can be constructed by composition of these first order operators.

3.5.1. THE LAPLACE EQUATION

We will start with an investigation of the simplest equation that can be formulated within this framework: the homogenous Laplace equation for some scalar potential P .

$$\nabla \cdot \nabla P = 0 \tag{3.11}$$

Expressing P as a dual 0-form, the DEC equivalent is:

$$d * \delta P = 0 \tag{3.12}$$

Which can be expressed diagrammatically as in figure 3.9.

Diagram of scalar div-grad Laplacian on a 2D manifold

Note that there is only one possible way to compose these operators. There is only one way to obtain the gradient of the potential field, only one way to transform it into a normal-flux representation, and only one way to find the divergence of this field. The input and output to this composed operator are forms of the same cardinality, which implies a square system matrix.

Recall the choice of signs in the exterior derivative, $\delta = -d^T$. The product dd^T has positive diagonal, so $d * \delta$ has negative diagonal, which is consistent with a Laplacian stencil.

3.5.2. PROOF OF POSEDNESS

Consideration of boundaries is delegated to later sections, since it introduces complications. First, consider a domain without boundary, say, the surface of a sphere.

The dual 0-form P may be given a physical interpretation as thermal energy density. The dual exterior derivative applied to P yields a dual 1-form, corresponding to the tangential flux between dual vertices. The Hodge star transforms these tangential fluxes into normal fluxes. Applying the primal exterior derivative to it yields a primal 2-form, representing the divergence of flux.

First we ask: what is the right-nullspace of δ ? Or, what does the condition $\delta x = 0$ imply about x ?

We recall the structure of δ : each equation corresponds to an edge, with two non-zero terms, +1 and -1. Equating the outcome of δx with zero, we can interpret these equations as a set of equality statements between the elements of x .

We can pick one arbitrary dual vertex v and its associated value $x(v)$. Following one of its incident edges, one arrives at a new vertex v' . Thus we see that $x(v) = x(v')$ must hold, for any two adjacent vertices .

By repeating this process $n-1$ times, we can assert equality between all elements of x . We should have at least that many edges/equations should we have a well-formed manifold: all excess equations must be linearly dependent, by independence of the chosen path over this graph of edges.

We conclude that right-nullspace of δ is of dimension one, and we can span it by a vector of constant values. A physical interpretation of this fact is, that whatever dynamics are suggested by the operator δ , they are insensitive to addition of a constant vector. The value of a potential is physically irrelevant, its gradient is important.

By definition of duality, $\delta = d^T$, we can draw the same conclusions concerning the left-nullspace of d : it is of dimension one, and it is spanned by a constant vector. By considering the singular value decomposition of δ , we see that the Laplace operator thus formulated has a null-space of rank one. The Hodge operator does not play a role in this argument concerning existence of solutions, since it is by definition a positive definite bijective mapping.

We conclude that, aside from this 1-dimensional null-space, the Laplace problem on a closed space is well-defined. This is in complete agreement with expectations for a Laplace operator on a closed domain. An illustration of the solution of a differential equation on a spherical domain is given in figure 3.10: this result will be discussed in the results section.

Figure 3.10

A spherical harmonic

3.5.3. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The above considerations were presented for a closed domain, where Poincare duality holds. Yet as has been argued, in a domain with a boundary, this duality does not hold.

In order to gain insight into the structure of a set of equations, we write it in first-order form, such as to reveal all the quantities that may play a role. The Laplace equation (3.11) expressed as a system of first order equations reads:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -I & \vec{\nabla} \\ \vec{\nabla} \cdot & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{F} \\ P \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (3.13)$$

Analogously, the Laplace equation in exterior calculus (3.12) written in first-order form reads:

$$\begin{bmatrix} - * & \delta \\ d & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F \\ P \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (3.14)$$

With P a dual 0-form, and F the normal flux, a primal $n-1$ -form.

This notation emphasizes the symmetric nature of the Laplace equation. The off-diagonal terms are actually skew-symmetric, but this symmetry is easily restored by negating the lower equation; this argument will be implicit in later discussions.

The block substructuring in terms of $[i,p,d]$, developed in chapter 2.3 can be introduced into this linear system of equations. Implementational generalizations drive the use of a 3×3 block, even when not all of this information is needed. The nonexistent rows and columns are still included in the symbolic representation, to retain the parallel with the numerical results.

Further, an Ansatz is made: it is assumed that the system including boundary conditions, is square; every variable is matched by an equation. That is, we do not assume the problem of finding well-posed boundary conditions is inherently unsolvable.

The discrete differential forms are extended over the dual boundary as the input to the exterior derivative demands. For instance: calculating the gradient everywhere requires a value of the potential to be known on every vertex, including those on the dual boundary. Just as the closure of these edges demands an additional vertex, so do the differential operator derived from this topology matrix demand a value at this vertex.

Yet the differential equations are not extended to the dual boundary: all equations corresponding to dual boundary cells are left zero for the moment.

$$\begin{bmatrix} - * & 0 & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & - * & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & \pm I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ (d) & (d) & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & 0 & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Fi \\ Fp \\ Fd \\ Pi \\ Pp \\ Pd \end{bmatrix} = rhs \quad (3.15)$$

(The terms in brackets are subblocks of the corresponding differential operator.)

We note that rows and columns corresponding to Pp are naturally empty, since there are no primal boundary n -elements. Fd does exist, but the primal 1-form is not extended to it: doing so would be both mathematically and physically meaningless. We might calculate the tangent flux between boundary points, but this information is never required. The empty columns and corresponding rows are marked with a dot. The rows/equations corresponding to Pd , primal boundary edges, or dual boundary vertices, are yet unspecified.

The resultant matrix is nearly symmetric, up to the identity term, which was introduced to close the dual manifold. The 'missing' term for symmetry is an identity matrix in the empty row, to be multiplied with Fp : the normal-flux on the boundary. That is; *making the matrix symmetric corresponds to setting Neumann boundary conditions.*

Alternatively, one can regain symmetry indirectly, by setting the lower-right block to some diagonal. This corresponds to specifying the values of Pd on the boundary, or Dirichlet boundary conditions. This allows one to trivially eliminate its associated rows and columns from the system. After this reduction, the identity term in the dual exterior derivative drops out, and we similarly end up with a symmetric system.

In general, we conjecture the most general well posed boundary condition to be of the form

$$\alpha Pd + \beta Fp = rhs \quad (3.16)$$

With α and β diagonal matrices, with only non-negative coefficients on the diagonal: $\alpha_{ii} \geq 0$, $\beta_{ii} \geq 0$, such that no trivial equations are formed, $\alpha_{ii} + \beta_{ii} > 0$.

That is, Robin boundary conditions; a linear combination of the unknowns in each boundary primal-dual pair. Note that the dual boundary vertices taking part in this boundary condition, are generated by the primal boundary edges that form the basis of the counterpart in this boundary condition. In this sense, apples and apples are being compared, and not scalars and vectors for instance.

$$\begin{bmatrix} - * & 0 & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & - * & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & \pm I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ (d) & (d) & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & \pm I \beta & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Fi \\ Fp \\ Fd \\ Pi \\ Pp \\ Pd \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \cdot \\ source \\ \cdot \\ rhs \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.17)$$

The terms involving interior variables do obviously not take part in the boundary conditions, which justifies the two zero blocks in the boundary condition. The constraint that α and β be diagonal matrices corresponds physically to exclusion of action-at-a-distance: we do not consider direct relations between variables in different points on the boundary, only local boundary conditions.

Note that such a generalized boundary condition similarly allows a reduction to symmetric form. Zero terms in β permit the reduction of the corresponding equation and variable. Non-zero terms in β can be eliminated such that the asymmetry is absorbed into the diagonal, which is always symmetric.

The coefficients on the diagonals of α and β can always be taken positive. Correct sign conventions are then imposed by multiplying the off-diagonal β with its opposing term, which is an identity matrix up to sign conventions. Negative β prohibits a proof of well-posedness. This restriction on the signs of the coefficients is in full agreement with a physical interpretation: ‘the higher the temperature inside the domain, the more heat should flow into it’ is not something we should expect to be able to prove to be well posed. This constraint is typically not mentioned in discussion of Robin boundary conditions, but it is not a peculiarity of discretization, but dictated by the physics of the problem, as shown in the proceeding section, also a mathematical requirement; a requirement for the diagonal dominance of these equations.

Figure 3.11

Sparsity structure of Laplace equation in first order form, with mixed boundary conditions. Dual tangent fluxes are included as an implementational convenience, but their corresponding trivial equations are entirely orthogonal to the equations of interest. They can be removed from the system, but they do not interfere with any solution algorithm.

3.5.4. REDUCTION TO SECOND ORDER FORM

The top row is easily inverted, due to the diagonal structure of the Hodge star. Therefore, we can explicitly express F as a function of P . Without loss of generality, Hodge stars will from now on be set to identity, to avoid notational clutter (this has a physical interpretation as a tensor grid with unit squares, having unit area and unit edge lengths).

We recall the Laplace equation including Robin boundary conditions:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -I & 0 & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & -I & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & \pm I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ (d) & (d) & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & \pm I\beta & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Fi \\ Fp \\ Fd \\ Pi \\ Pp \\ Pd \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \cdot \\ div \\ \cdot \\ rhs \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.18)$$

Which we may write as:

$$Lx = b \quad (3.19)$$

The unknowns in the first order system can be expressed purely in terms of the merely the potential.

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} F \\ P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta \\ I \end{bmatrix} [P] = Rr \quad (3.20)$$

With a transformation matrix R expanded as:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} (\delta) & \cdot & 0 \\ (\delta) & \cdot & \pm I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ I & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & \cdot & I \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.21)$$

Substitution equation 3.20 into 3.19 gives:

$$LRr = b \quad (3.22)$$

Expanding this product:

$$LR = \begin{bmatrix} -I & 0 & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & -I & \cdot & (\delta) & \cdot & \pm I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ (d) & (d) & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & \pm I\beta & \cdot & 0 & \cdot & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} (\delta) & \cdot & 0 \\ (\delta) & \cdot & \pm I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ I & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & \cdot & I \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.23)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ d\delta & \cdot & \pm dI \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \pm I\beta\delta & \cdot & \alpha + \beta \end{bmatrix}$$

Multiplying from the left with R transposed, we get:

$$R^T LR = Dr = R^T b \quad (3.25)$$

Where D is the Laplace operator in second order form, including boundary conditions. It reduces to:

$$D = R^T LR = \begin{bmatrix} (d)(\delta) & \cdot & \pm(d)I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \pm I\beta(\delta) & \cdot & \alpha + \beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.26)$$

3.5.5. DIAGONAL DOMINANCE

In the upper left corner of D we have a familiar Laplace stencil (5-point on a 2D tensor grid). The term in the upper right is contained in the upper left as well, so this term can not violate the diagonal dominance of these rows. Whatever nonzero it has on a row, appears multiplied by itself, thus with positive sign, on the diagonal as well.

Both α and β are nonnegative, and their sum is guaranteed to be positive. The lower-left term involving only β can not violate diagonal dominance. By inspecting its topological meaning we see that it can have at most one nonzero per row. Therefore, the bottom row of equations is diagonally dominant too.

If we would not demand non-negativity from both α and β , then we could not guarantee diagonal dominance, but neither are such boundary conditions physically permissible. Enforcing sign conventions by requiring symmetry in the sign of the β with its opposite term, positivity of the diagonal is ensured, as $(\pm I)\beta(\pm I) = \beta$.

Since the presented reduction involves no approximations, well posedness of the reduced system implies well posedness of the first order system, and vice versa. One property of diagonal dominance is that it guarantees convergence of Jacobi iterations. The equations thus posed can therefore not be over constrained. Pure Neumann conditions restore symmetry and thus Poincare duality, leading to the same posedness as on a closed domain (well posed up to a constant vector), and adding weight to the diagonal of a positive-semi-definite matrix can only reduce the nullspace. It is not hard to see that by adding one constraint on the potential itself, rather than just its derivatives, the solution is uniquely specified.

3.6. VECTOR LAPLACIAN

In vector calculus one can distinguish between a Laplacian operator Δ , and a vector Laplacian $\vec{\Delta}$. The vector Laplacian obeys the identity $\vec{\Delta} = \nabla \nabla \cdot - \nabla \times \nabla \times$.

In exterior calculus, the same operator is known as the Laplace-de Rham operator, and it is defined as $\Delta = d\delta + \delta d$. Applied to 0-forms, it reduces to the Laplace operator. The difference in sign is due to vector calculus only recognizing one curl operator, even though they are perhaps better regarded as two operators, as the 2D case emphasizes.

3.7. VERTEX-CENTERED LAPLACIAN

On every manifold we can formulate two distinct scalar Laplacians: one over primal 0-forms, and one over dual 0-forms. Vertex or cell centered Laplacians, as one might say from a finite-difference perspective.

Given the stated conventions, the vertex-centered Laplacian in 2D corresponds to a curl-curl Laplacian. The relation between streamfunction and vorticity is given by two consecutive curl operators, which is displayed in figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12

In vector calculus, this would be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \nabla \times \\ \nabla \times & -I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ F \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.25)$$

In exterior calculus, this would be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \delta \\ d & -* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ F \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.26)$$

Expanding the substructure and applying boundary conditions, we obtain:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdot & (\delta) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdot & (\delta) & (\delta) & \pm I \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ (d) & (d) & \cdot & -* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (d) & \cdot & 0 & -* & 0 \\ 0 & \pm I\beta & \cdot & 0 & 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_i \\ \phi_p \\ \cdot \\ F_i \\ F_p \\ F_d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega \\ \omega \\ \cdot \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ rhs \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.27)$$

This Laplacian suggests boundary conditions, which are difficult to give any physical interpretation to. Although numerical experiments confirm they are well-posed for any coefficients, reducing this Laplacian, including general boundary conditions to an easily solvable system, is not as simple as for the cell-centered Laplacian. In contrast to the face-centered Laplacian, the flux cannot be fully expressed as a function of the potential, and therefore, it cannot be eliminated in the same way as for the cell-centered Laplacian.

If this Laplacian is however used to compute a streamfunction from given flux data, the boundary equation and corresponding column can be completely eliminated, after which the equations can be fully expressed in terms of the streamfunction. This is the context in which it has been used in the present work, so this subtle difference does not introduce any complications.

3.8. CONCLUSIONS

3.8.1. LIMITATIONS

The exterior derivative offers a calculus analogous to vector calculus. Using these constructions, general tensor relations cannot be expressed. Exterior calculus as a whole is equivalent to tensor calculus, but this is dependent on the introduction of the exterior product, or wedge product [3], which will not be discussed here.

3.8.2. APPLICATIONS

Yet with this minimal set of operators defined, all problems of pure vector calculus can be expressed. This includes the Laplace equation and the Stokes equation, but not for instance the Navier-Stokes equations, as the advection term $\vec{\nabla} \vec{u}$ is tensorial in nature.

A discretization of the fourth order harmonic equation can be obtained in a similar manner, by composition of four operators, making multiple loops in the diagram.

Of particular elegance is the formulation of Maxwell's equations of electrodynamics in an exterior calculus framework. Expressed in vector calculus, they form a set of four partial differential equations. In exterior calculus, one can define a 'Maxwell 2-form' F over a 3+1 dimensional space-time manifold, and the Maxwell equations in the vacuum then reduce to $dF = 0$, $\delta * F = J$. In the discrete calculus setting, this directly reproduces the defacto-standard leapfrog/staggered Yee-scheme of computational electrodynamics, and provides extensions and new insight to it. [11]

Similar concepts can be used to obtain a mimetic discrete analogue of Einstein's equations of gravity. This goes by the name of Regge calculus, an idea preceding DEC by decades.

3.8.3. RELATION TO DISCRETIZATION METHODS

Applied to a tensor grid, the stencil thus obtained in the interior is the same as obtained from a staggered finite difference scheme. In fluid dynamics, this is equivalent to the MAC scheme, and in electrodynamics, the Yee scheme. It extends these schemes trivially to non-uniform meshes, in which case there is an equivalence with some finite volume and mixed finite element formulations.

Non-constant coefficients can be accounted for as an additional positive-definite transformation between fluxes, that can be contracted into the Hodge star. [12]

4. APPLICATIONS TO COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS

4.1. THE NAVIER-STOKES EQUATIONS

The Navier-Stokes equations are a continuum model of physical fluid flow phenomena, and it is a powerful model of all fluid flows permitting a continuum approach.

In partial differential equation form, the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations in a stationary Cartesian frame, for a Newtonian fluid read:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \rho \vec{u} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{u} + \vec{\nabla} P - \mu \Delta \vec{u} = \vec{f} \quad (4.1)$$

With an incompressibility condition:

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u} = 0 \quad (4.2)$$

They form a system of nonlinear equations. The non-linear term in particular makes these equations difficult to solve. One way to facilitate this process, is by operator splitting.

4.2. OPERATOR SPLITTING

A system of differential equations written in terms of differential operators:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = O_1(u) + O_2(u) \quad (4.3)$$

can be solved by separately considering equations of the form:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = O_1(u), \frac{du}{dt} = O_2(u) \quad (4.4)$$

By sequentially evolving the solution according to each operator every timestep, one obtains a numerical scheme that converges to the unsplit case, with an associated error, called the splitting error that is for a simple alternating scheme, quadratic in time [16].

Applying this splitting to momentum equation of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations (Eq 4.1), we can obtain two separate vector equations. One of them the time-dependent Stokes equation:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} P - \mu \Delta \vec{u} = \vec{f} \quad (4.5)$$

And the other term containing only the self-advection.

$$\frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \vec{u} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{u} = 0 \quad (4.6)$$

The self-advection equation (Eq 4.6) can be written as a vorticity advection equation by taking the curl of this equation.

Expressing Eq 4.6 in a frame moving with the flow using the material derivative, we obtain the incompressible invicid vorticity advection equation:

$$D\vec{\omega} = (\vec{\omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla})\vec{u} \quad (4.7)$$

This expresses the advection of vorticity. The right hand side contains a so-called stretching term, representing the change in vorticity due to stretching of the fluid medium.

Kelvin's circulation theorem expresses the same relation, concerning the conservation of vorticity, in terms of the vorticity around a closed loop advected with the flow: the loop does not only move with, but also stretches with the flow, which allows one to state the essence of advection even more directly, as:

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dt} = 0 \quad (4.8)$$

$$\Gamma = \oint_{C(t)} \vec{u} \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (4.9)$$

The time-dependent Stokes equations form a linear system of partial differential equations. Kelvin's circulation theorem contains the nonlinearity, as both the domain of integration and its integrand are a function of velocity.

4.3. PREVIOUS WORK

4.3.1 SEMI-LAGRANGIAN ADVECTION

In [4], DEC is used to construct a very simple unconditionally stable semi-Lagrangian advection scheme for the vorticity advection equation, which adheres to Kelvin's circulation theorem by construction. A semi-Lagrangian scheme is characterized by an Eulerian grid on which the unknowns are located. The grid is advected with the flow in a Lagrangian fashion, but at the end of every timestep, the advected solution is projected back onto the stationary grid. This avoids both the relative complexity of discretizing and solving an Eulerian advection stencil, and the difficulty with remeshing and changing connectivity inherent to pure Lagrangian methods.

Figure 4.1

Color gradient advected with 2D Flow past a disc, illustration taken from [4]

The mesh itself is advected with the flow over a timestep, and with the help of this construction, the advected quantity is mapped from the current to the advanced state. By Kelvin's circulation theorem, it is known that the circulation/vorticity around an advected loop must be constant, and the aim is to advect this vorticity.

Figure 4.2

Regular square (dual) mesh advected in a lid-driven cavity, by a Stokes flow. This deformation provides a geometric visualization of the transformation advected fields will undergo.

A common method to accomplish vorticity advection, is by 'velocity advection', with a divergence constraint. This is a misnomer, as velocity is not actually a convected quantity: it is not constant along streamlines. Velocity advection requires a subsequent 'pressure correction' or divergence constraint. Using DEC, it can be shown that 'velocity advection with pressure correction' is exactly equivalent to satisfying a discrete analog of Kelvin's circulation theorem. By the discrete Helmholtz-Hodge theorem [3], we know that any 1-form can be represented exactly by the gradient of a scalar potential and the curl of a streamfunction, plus an harmonic term. Therefore, advecting velocity, and then subtracting the divergent component, is equivalent to sampling velocity, and taking the curl of the result, i.e. constant vorticity along advected loops.

4.3.2 BFECC

A shortcoming of this method is the numerical diffusion introduced in mapping the advected fields between timesteps. The method described in [4] has numerical diffusion first-order in space, which is insufficient for most applications in engineering.

Backward-Forward error correction and compensation (BFECC) provides a way to extend this simple scheme to higher-order accuracy. A pure advection equation is time symmetric: evolving it through some closed path in time, should have no net result. This time-symmetry is a property that the discrete equations should seek to mimic, if they are to accurately model advection.

The idea behind BFECC is simple: evolve the state forward in time, evolve the state backward in time. The difference is an indicator for all accrued error components, which can be subtracted from the initial state, to be advected forward in time again to yield an improved final advected state. This can be shown to raise the rate of convergence of numerical dissipation to second order [5].

Figure 4.3

A scalar step function advected over a periodic domain with 20 gridpoints. Left: semi-Lagrangian advection as in [4]. Right, the same scheme raised to second order accuracy using BFECC

The black line is the initial profile; a step function, the dark-grey line the profile after 10 advection cycles across the domain, the light-gray line the profile after 100 advection-cycles.

With first order diffusion, the initial profile all but disappears over 100 cycles. With second order accuracy, components with a 20 cell wavelength hardly attenuate.

This comes at a factor three in computational expense, yet adds hardly any conceptual complexity, while retaining the circulation preserving property. The resulting scheme is not strictly monotone, but is unconditionally stable. Evaluating the combination of these techniques was the original goal of this thesis, but it has been abandoned in favor of exploring the link between discrete calculus and boundary conditions. This combination of techniques has recently been successfully implemented in [1]

4.3.3. EULERIAN ADVECTION

In [1], an Eulerian, energy preserving advection scheme is derived from DEC principles. Demanding the discrete advection operator respects key characteristics of an advection operator, such as skew symmetry, provides a way to derive a scheme which can guarantee energy conservation and exact time-symmetry.

Figure 4.4

A comparison of various solvers for the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. (text and image verbatim citation from [1])

It should be noted that the presented scheme does not depend on higher order reconstructions. This makes it straightforward to implement without problematic boundary terms, and gives a compact stencil leading to a system of equations that is comparatively easy to solve. It can be regarded as an extension of the Harlow and Welch's scheme to unstructured grids.

This is one good example in support of the view often expressed in DEC literature, that respecting key algebraic invariants, is a good guide to arriving at qualitatively well-behaved discrete equations [17]. The presented scheme is only second order accurate, but its long term behavior is very similar to the high-order spectral reference solution.

Another paper on the derivation of Eulerian advection stencils guided by insights from exterior calculus can be found in [15]

5. STOKES EQUATIONS

5.1. INTRODUCTION

Further emphasis will be on the Stokes equations. The Stokes equations have direct applications, involving low-Reynolds flows such as found in roller bearings or polymer flows. Aside from direct applications, it can also arise as a sub-problem while solving the Navier-Stokes equations by means of operator splitting.

5.2. FIRST-ORDER FORM

We recall the definition of the vector Laplacian operator:

$$\vec{\Delta} = \vec{\nabla} \vec{\nabla} \cdot - \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{\nabla} \times \quad (5.1)$$

That is, the divergence of the gradient, minus the curl of the curl.

Invoking the definition of curl and the vector Laplacian on Eq 4.5, we may write the time dependent Stokes equations as:

$$\vec{\omega} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{u} \quad (5.2)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} P + \mu \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{\omega} = \vec{f} \quad (5.3)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u} = 0 \quad (5.4)$$

That is, a system of linear first order differential equations with three unknown fields, $\vec{\omega}$, \vec{u} and P . The curl of vorticity is linearly related to shear stress. Arranging equations 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4 in matrix form (with I an identity transform), and omitting constants for clarity, we get:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -I & \vec{\nabla} \times \\ \vec{\nabla} \times & \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \\ \vec{\nabla} \cdot & \vec{\nabla} \cdot \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{\omega} \\ \vec{u} \\ P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{0} \\ \vec{f} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.5)$$

Analogously, in discrete exterior calculus, equation 5.5 would be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} - * & * \delta \\ d * & \Delta t & * \delta \\ d * & & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega \\ u \\ P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ f \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.6)$$

In this representation, pressure is a dual 0-form, flux a dual 1-form, and vorticity a dual 2-form. This applies equally in two and three dimensions. In 2D, vorticity is a scalar field, and in 3D, it will be a

vector field, but this has no impact on the structure of these equations, from the exterior calculus point of view. These relations are expressed diagrammatically in figure 5.1.

Geometric location of variables and equations in either two or three dimensions

We see immediately that the equations thus posed are structurally symmetric by definition of duality. The Hodge operators forced by this choice of locating variables and equations breaks symmetry, but it could be recovered by appropriate scaling rows and columns, if so desired.

The Δt term represents some discrete time derivative operator. If an implicit trapezoidal scheme is employed, this term would take the form of a diagonal matrix scaled by the inverse of the timestep. For large timestep, the Stokes equations for steady flow are recovered.

5.3. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The recipe for obtaining well posed boundary conditions for the Laplace equation can be generalized and extended to the Stokes equations.

GENERALIZED RECIPE

- Write the governing equations in first order form, such as to expose all variables that may play a role.
- Extend forms over the dual boundary as mathematically and physically called for by the differential operators
- Assume a square matrix: one equation for every variable, such that the system may be well posed
- Put differential equations in all rows associated with interior, or primal cells.
- Put boundary conditions in all rows introduced as part of topologically closing the dual manifold, in such a way as to restore symmetry

Without loss of generality, we disregard the time-operator and Hodge operators, and introduce substructuring into the system. Applying this recipe to equation 5.6, equation 5.7 is obtained.

$$\begin{bmatrix} -I & 0 & \cdot & (\delta) & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & -I & \cdot & (\delta) & (\delta) & \pm I & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ (d) & (d) & \cdot & 0 & 0 & 0 & (\delta) & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & (d) & \cdot & 0 & 0 & 0 & (\delta) & \cdot & \mp I \\ 0 & \pm I \sigma & \cdot & 0 & 0 & \tau & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & 0 & \cdot & (d) & (d) & 0 & 0 & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ 0 & 0 & \cdot & 0 & \mp I \beta & 0 & 0 & \cdot & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_i \\ \omega_p \\ \omega_d \\ u_i \\ u_p \\ u_d \\ P_i \\ P_p \\ P_d \end{bmatrix} = rhs \quad (5.7)$$

(note: the terms in brackets denote nonzero sub-blocks in the corresponding operators, not the complete exterior derivative itself)

Rows and columns corresponding to ω_d and P_p are empty: there are no primal boundary n-cells, nor dual boundary n-cells.

Each primal exterior derivative has an empty block row. We thus see that symmetry demands that each application of a primal exterior derivative requires a boundary condition: one for the Laplace equation, and two for the Stokes equations. Symmetry can be recovered by including an off-diagonal term on vorticity on the boundary, and pressure on the boundary.

The pressure term acts on the extension of the pressure dual 0-form to the boundary. These dual vertices are geometrically related to primal n-1-primitives: primal edges or faces in 2D and 3D respectively. The variable located there is normal flux, thus we may postulate a relation between these variables as a local relation, without comparing apples and oranges, or invoking action-at-a-distance. The boundary condition thus obtained is a relation between pressure and normal flux, the well-known 'porosity' boundary condition.

This boundary condition could be expressed algebraically as:

$$\alpha P + \beta \vec{u} \cdot \vec{n} = rhs \quad (5.8)$$

Similarly, symmetry demands a condition on the extension of the velocity dual 1-form to the boundary, or tangent flux along the boundary. These dual boundary edges are geometrically related to a primal n-2-primitives: primal vertices or edges in 2D and 3D respectively. The variable located there is vorticity, thus by the same logic, we may pose a local relation between tangent flux and (cotangent) vorticity on the boundary.

This boundary condition could be expressed algebraically as:

$$\sigma \vec{\omega} \cdot \vec{c} + \tau \vec{u} \cdot \vec{t} = rhs \quad (5.9)$$

By cotangent vorticity, the vorticity around a cotangent direction \vec{c} is meant. In three dimensions, a coordinate system on a surface may be described in terms of a normal, a tangent direction, and a second tangent direction, orthogonal to the tangent, named the cotangent. Thus the set of vectors including the normal, tangent and cotangent vectors, are all orthonormal.

A 3D discrete manifold will have a 2D boundary, having primal-dual edge-edge pairs. These edges are orthogonal. The primal edge will serve as a basis for the vorticity, and the dual edge as a basis for tangent flux. Hence the label cotangent vorticity: cotangent relative to the tangent flux, to which it is orthogonal. In 2D the primal-dual pair is a vertex-edge pair, and vorticity, including the vorticity on the boundary will be a 0-form instead of a 1-form; a scalar instead of a vector.

One can make the system including boundary conditions symmetric, entirely analogous to the Laplace equation. Non-zero terms on the off-diagonal permit a row-scaling to exact symmetry, and zero terms on the off-diagonal imply a non-zero term on the diagonal, which permits the elimination of the asymmetric rows and columns.

5.4. RELATION TO PREVIOUS WORK

The porosity condition thus found is a natural extension of the Robin boundary condition for the Laplace equation, and as such long since recognized.

Boundary conditions on tangent velocity are similarly common in fluid dynamics, so called no-slip boundary conditions, prescribing a velocity equal to one imposed by a moving boundary. Another boundary condition often encountered is the symmetry boundary condition: a (typically homogenous) condition on the normal derivative of tangent velocity at the boundary. Demanding the normal derivative of tangent velocity to be zero, combined with zero normal flux, corresponds to imposing a symmetry plane.

The link between a vorticity boundary condition and a symmetry condition can be seen from the definition of (2D) vorticity as $\omega = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}$, or in terms of a coordinate system aligned with the boundary, $\omega = \frac{\partial u_t}{\partial n} - \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial t}$. Clearly, vorticity and normal derivative of tangent velocity are not independent conditions. Demanding zero normal flux and zero non-normal vorticity does similarly correspond to a symmetry plane, as vorticity is linearly related to shear stress, which should be zero at a symmetry line.

That vorticity and tangent flux, like pressure and normal flux should participate in one generalized boundary condition is suggested by the topological relation between the location of these variables. Tangent flux lives on the primitives introduced as duals of the primal boundary, which guarantees they are related one to one: There exist an equal number of boundary tangent fluxes as boundary vorticities, since they are related by duality. A relation between, say, pressure and vorticity does not make sense, as the set of primitives on which they live are not related, and are in general not even equal in quantity.

As with the Laplace equation, sign conventions are naturally enforced by demanding symmetry with the boundary term in the dual exterior derivative. Physical considerations demand a restriction on the permissible signs of the coefficients of the boundary conditions. An increased pressure gradient

is physically associated with an increased normal flux; the converse implies negative diffusion. If this physical requirement is broken, so should be our expectation of a well posed system of equations. Similarly, the shear stress to tangent flux condition should obey a restriction on sign. The physics of the problem suggest the resulting matrix ought to have only real nonzero eigenvalues. This can be shown to hold in practice by extending the conclusions drawn for the Laplace problem by numerical calculation of eigenvalues for the cases studied, but a concise proof of this being true for the suggested choice of boundary conditions has not been found.

A prior discovery of this form of boundary conditions has been found in a paper published in 2003 [7], Here, the same boundary condition between tangent flux and cotangent vorticity is derived from an algebraic point of view. The boundary conditions derived from a discrete topological perspective do thus agree with continuum calculus, although as is typical with algebraic treatment of the boundary conditions of the Laplace problem, no mention is made of restrictions on the signs of the coefficients.

The authors remarked ‘We do not have a simple physical interpretation of this boundary condition’. A simple physical interpretation is obtained by drawing the relation between vorticity and shear stress: given a constant normal flux, $\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial t} = 0$, vorticity is proportional to $\frac{\partial u_t}{\partial n}$. Thus, we may interpret this boundary condition as representing a generalized relation between tangent flux and shear strain-rate, or shear stress, which agrees with intuition: Dragging the fluid along at some prescribed velocity should cause a reaction force, and forcing the fluid with an external force should lead to a proportional velocity in the same direction. Both boundary conditions are similar, in that they express a relation between force and movement, in complementary directions.

The conditions on vorticity, after vorticity is eliminated and the problem is entirely expressed in terms of fluxes, form a nontrivial stencil. Just as this boundary condition has proven hard to find from the continuum velocity-pressure formulation, so it is understandable that it has not been noticed in any discrete analogues of the same velocity-pressure formulation.

Another paper from mid 2009 [1], which has come to my attention only recently while documenting my own findings, arrive at similar conclusions. The equations are written in first order form for the sake of deriving an energy-preserving advection stencil. No attempt at theoretical justification is given, but the one-to-one correspondence between boundary normal fluxes and boundary pressure on the one hand, and tangent fluxes and cotangent vorticities is noted. Boundary conditions on these variables are imposed for the Navier-Stokes equations, and solutions are successfully obtained in both two and three dimensions.

5.5. NUMERICAL CONSIDERATIONS

5.5.1. REDUCTION TO SECOND-ORDER FORM

Like the Laplace equation in first order form, the Stokes equations in first order form contain an equation that is easily eliminated from the system. The equation relating flux and vorticity has a full diagonal, thus an exact inverse can be obtained, and any expression involving vorticity can be substituted for one in terms of flux, without loss of information.

By doing so, a smaller system of equations is obtained, better suited to numerical solution, while correctly propagating the boundary conditions derived from the first-order form.

In linear algebraic terms, we can formulate a reduction matrix with the following structure:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega \\ u \\ P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta & 0 \\ I & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u \\ P \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.10)$$

Left and right multiplying the Stokes equations in first order form (Eq. 5.6) with this transform, a 2x2 system in terms of flux and pressure is obtained

$$\begin{bmatrix} d & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -I & \delta & 0 \\ d & 0 & \delta \\ 0 & d & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta & 0 \\ I & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} d\delta & \delta \\ d & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.11)$$

It should be noted that the solution to the system

$$\begin{bmatrix} d\delta & \delta \\ d & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.12)$$

and the system

$$\begin{bmatrix} d\delta + \delta d & \delta \\ d & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.13)$$

are identical, due to the incompressibility condition, $du = 0$. For numerical purposes, using the full vector Laplacian, including the δd term, or gradient of divergence, is preferable. The convergence behavior of the system with full vector Laplacian has been found to be superior, for the iterative solver employed. Not only is the convergence behavior superior, at least for a regular tensor grid, the resultant stencil is more sparse than the alternative, as illustrated in figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2

Stencil of the curl of vorticity, the gradient of divergence, and the full vector Laplacian on a regular grid respectively. In the interior, the vector Laplacian derived this way is the familiar five-point stencil over a staggered grid. Near the boundary, a correct stencil will arise, not requiring any special attention.

5.5.2. DISTRIBUTED RELAXATION

Distributed relaxation (DR) is a technique for solving saddle-point, or semi-definite problems, such as the Stokes problem. The divergence equation is, for an incompressible fluid, not a function of pressure, but has zeros on the diagonal. As such, iterative methods based on an inversion of the diagonal, or other sparse approximate inverses, are not directly applicable.

The theoretical argument underlying DR is that the Stokes equations are mathematically an elliptic system of equations. Elliptic problems are known to be efficiently solvable using simple smoothers, so we should seek a transformation that exposes these elliptical properties of the linear system. [6], [8], [9]

A system of equations S can be right preconditioned by a transformation matrix P to yield a transformed system S' .

$$S' = SP \tag{5.14}$$

This transformation establishes a relation between the unknowns and the unknowns of the transformed system. Given a solution in terms of the transformed variables, the original unknowns can be explicitly recovered.

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ P \end{bmatrix} = P \begin{bmatrix} u' \\ P' \end{bmatrix} \tag{5.15}$$

Rather than performing a solution in terms of the transformed variables, this transformation is used to derive an iterative update in terms of the original variables.

DR can be expressed algorithmically as:

- Calculate the residual belonging to the current iterate of the untransformed variables
- Use a residual correction method on the transformed equations to suggest a step in terms of the transformed variables
- Achieve the residual correction by distributing this correction to the untransformed variables

The characteristics of this iteration are those of the relaxation step applied to the transformed system.

In [19], Jesse Slot notes on distributed relaxation:

“A disadvantage of this method is that it needs factorizable discretizations. So far, distributed relaxation has only been applied to finite difference discretizations. Although, in theory it can also be used for unstructured meshes, little is published on those topics.”

If the discrete equations are obtained by means of DEC, all factorized terms are directly available, and DR can be expressed purely in terms of linear algebra, applying equally well to discretizations over unstructured meshes or curved domains. The availability of such mimetic discrete operators can be useful in the construction of other solution methods as well [18].

The algebraic properties of discrete calculus, allow us to formulate the DR transformation entirely in terms of discrete operators already at our disposal. The mimetic properties of discrete calculus guarantees this will yield the desired result.

The usual DR transform for the Stokes equations can be written in DEC as:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} I & \delta \\ 0 & d\delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.16)$$

Were the lower-right term takes the form of a scalar Laplacian, and the top-right term can be interpreted as a gradient operator.

Applied to the Stokes equation (Eq.5.6), this gives:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \delta d + d\delta & \delta \\ d & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & \delta \\ 0 & d\delta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta d + d\delta & (\delta d + d\delta)\delta + \delta d\delta \\ d & d\delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.17)$$

The upper right off-diagonal term can be made to vanish. The term $d\delta\delta = 0$ by the exact sequence property, and the remaining terms $\delta d\delta + \delta d\delta$ can be made to cancel exactly, by appropriate choice of signs in the transformation matrix.

The lower left term remains nonzero, but Jacobi iteration is not hindered by it: diagonal dominance is a sufficient but not necessary condition for the convergence of Jacobi iteration.

The diagonal terms are both Laplacian stencils, which are indeed as sought after, elliptic equations with a non-zero diagonal.

5.5.3. EXTENSION TO TIME-DEPENDENT CASE

If a time-dependent Stokes problem is solved using implicit timestepping, by for instance an implicit trapezoidal scheme, an extra diagonal term will appear. It is of the same sign as the diagonal of the vector Laplacian, so we should not expect this term to be able to compromise the well-posedness of the equations [6]. As a general principle, a more diagonally biased matrix is better conditioned, and easier to solve using iterative methods. However, it is found that the convergence of distributed relaxation is adversely affected by this term, failing to converge at all for small timesteps.

For a typical second-order accurate implicit midpoint time discretization, the time-dependent Stokes equations lead to a system of equations of the form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha I + \delta d + d\delta & \delta \\ d & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u \\ P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f \\ g \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.18)$$

The term αI appears due to the implicit time discretization.

If we were to apply the same transformation:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} I & \delta \\ 0 & d\delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.19)$$

The transformed system would be:

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha I + \delta d + d\delta & \delta \\ d & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & \delta \\ 0 & d\delta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha I + \delta d + d\delta & \alpha I \delta \\ 0 & d\delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.20)$$

That is, a nonzero term appears off-diagonal. The dual exterior derivative involved corresponds to the gradient of pressure: thus, it has two nonzero terms on every row, for only one on the diagonal. As such, diagonal dominance is increasingly compromised with increasing α , or decreasing Δt .

This off-diagonal term can be countered by the inclusion of another term in the transformation

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha I + \delta d + d\delta & \delta \\ d & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & \delta \\ 0 & \alpha I + d\delta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha I + \delta d + d\delta & \alpha(I\delta + \delta I) \\ 0 & d\delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.26)$$

Note the extra identity matrix in the lower-right term of the transformation matrix. Further, note that these are different identity matrices, having unequal number of rows and columns. Since Hodge operators have been omitted, it would seem as if this term can be eliminated exactly, but including Hodge stars, a term of the form $I * \delta + \delta * I$ would appear on the off-diagonal. The Hodge stars correspond to a scaling of rows and columns of δ respectively. The scaling from one side is not alterable, as it derives from the system matrix. The transformation matrix need not meet any physical constraints so we are free to choose it as desired, but in general, it may not be possible to design a scaling which makes the sum vanish exactly. Since this diagonal term also appears on the transformed diagonal, it need not vanish exactly, but only half of it in order to restore diagonal dominance.

For a regular grid, choosing this term such as to make it vanish everywhere is easy, and applied as such, the altered transformation achieves the intended result, of restoring the convergence to the time-independent case. Extensions to irregular grids have not been tested, but it seems plausible that this transformation could be made to work there as well.

5.5.4. DISTRIBUTED RELAXATION AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The presented DR transform cannot be successfully applied to the system including boundary conditions. The goal is a diagonally dominant transformed matrix, but the standard transformation fails to provide this property to the boundary equations. In general, it is common in literature on iterative solvers to consider the structure of the equations in the interior, [8], without any mention of how to proceed when additional equations specifying boundary conditions are included. This is not a problem if explicit boundary conditions are imposed, which permit elimination from the system, but if the boundary condition takes the form of a more general relation, this does become a nontrivial problem.

The reduction to second order form and distributed relaxation transformation can be contracted into one transformation. All transformations of the form in equation 5.21 have been tried (among others), where the constants denote scalar multiplication factors to be determined by imposing constraints on the terms to appear in the resultant reduced system, without arriving at a form that seemed provably diagonally dominant.

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} \delta & 0 \\ A I + B \delta d + C d \delta & D \delta \\ E d & F I + G d \delta + H a \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.21)$$

A curious fact is that the dual boundary topology terms never participate in the physical equations. They can be included in the preconditioning matrix, but it does no more seem to lead to a fully diagonally dominant system.

5.5.5. A HYBRID SOLUTION ALGORITHM

A hybrid iteration has been designed to obtain a solution algorithm. Distributed relaxation with a Jacobi or Gauss-Seidel smoother is applied to the equations in the interior of the domain, and a residual projection method is applied to the boundary conditions, which can be regarded as Jacobi iteration on the normal equations. This requires a back-substitution to find the variables on the dual boundary.

Algorithmically:

- Apply a distributed relaxation step to the interior
- Solve for the dual boundary variables ω_p and P_d
- Perform relaxation on the (normal) boundary equations

The boundary conditions are solved by a relaxation on the normal equations, or interpreted alternatively, by making the residual orthogonal to the equations. The normal equations of the boundary conditions are always a diagonal matrix, thus simply one smoothing step makes the boundary variables satisfy the boundary condition exactly.

The back-substitution is implemented as a residual projection too, as this is most convenient given the sparse nature of the matrices involved. First, the residual of the relevant equation is computed. The interior variables are then regarded as fixed, with the boundary variables as unknowns. This effectively leaves one with a diagonal system to solve.

6. NUMERICAL RESULTS (C++)

Most of the results obtained are derived from the MATLAB implementation. The C++ implementation has been abandoned in a stage where not many (polished) results could be obtained, but it implements various algorithms, which have not been implemented in MATLAB due to time constraints.

Most notably, the implementation of the smoothers discussed and their associated multi-grid solution algorithm has not been ported to MATLAB. It would have been a near-necessity in the context of repeated solutions for a time-stepped advection problem, requiring relatively high resolution, but for the validation of the presented theory concerning boundary conditions, modest meshes and direct solvers do suffice.

6.1. MULTIGRID CONVERGENCE

The multi-grid solver is a straightforward application of multi-grid to a problem in mixed formulation. Transfer operators for forms of any degree are derived from the mesh-subdivision algorithm. The only non-standard part, is that the dual boundary unknowns are not transferred, but obtained by back-substitution after transfer of the interior variables. Deriving additional transfer operators for the boundary unknowns would be another option, which has not been pursued.

It is shown that multi-grid performance is obtained for the time-dependent Stokes equations on a lid-driven cavity. No boundary conditions on vorticity are included, as these are not yet discovered at the time of implementation. The algorithm has not been aggressively optimized: it is run with both three pre and post smoothing steps, which leads to excellent convergence factors per sweep. No attempt has been made to optimize convergence versus FLOPs.

The finest grid is a 5 times refined square, thus having 64 faces on each side. The viscosity is set to unity, and the domain spans from -1 to +1. The timestep is set to 0.01 seconds, which for these parameters yields quasi-stationary behavior in four timesteps. The results of these steps are listed in figures 6.1.

Figure 6.1

Sweep\timestep	1	2	3	4
1	1.8e2	26	9.2	5.4
2	25	3.4	1.3	0.64
3	2.3	0.68	0.2	0.084
4	0.34	0.14	0.039	0.016
5	0.058	0.028	0.0079	0.0031
6	0.011	0.0059	0.0017	0.00067

Solution of the Time dependent stokes equations: convergence per sweep is a factor 5 or better.

We see that the proposed solver for the time-dependent Stokes equations converges. Convergence has been checked for the limiting cases $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta t \rightarrow \infty$, and this is found not to influence convergence significantly. In the limit to zero, a strongly dominating diagonal term appears, but this

does not lead to trivial convergence, as it appears only in the momentum equations, and the convergence then becomes limited by the strong coupling imposed by the conservation of mass.

Figure 6.2

Sweep\timestep	1	2	3	4
1	1.2e2	23	8	4.3
2	9.4	2.1	0.7	0.34
3	0.97	0.2	0.067	0.032
4	0.099	0.021	0.0069	0.0032
5	0.01	0.0022	0.00092	0.00058
6	0.0011	0.0005	0.00047	0.00047

Solution of the stream-function satisfying the flow field found above: convergence is roughly an order of magnitude per sweep

Over the same grid, a time-dependent diffusion equation is solved (for advection testing purposes). Boundary conditions are two opposing isolated walls, and two opposing walls with a prescribed constant temperature differential. The unified treatment of boundary conditions has not been implemented, but rather the ad-hoc projection algorithm is still used here. Although multigrid efficiency is obtained, the convergence is somewhat less than for the streamfunction solver, which might be attributed to the fact that the streamfunction problem involves only trivial boundary conditions.

Figure 6.3

Sweep\timestep	1	2	3	4
1	7.4e2	5.6e2	4.4e2	3.5e2
2	1.7e2	12	10	8.9
3	23	0.68	0.59	0.52
4	3.1	0.08	0.068	0.059
5	0.43	0.012	0.01	0.0088
6	0.064	0.0022	0.0019	0.0017

Time dependent diffusion: convergence per sweep is around a factor 8

6.2. PRELIMINARY ADVECTION RESULTS

Some preliminary advection results have been obtained. Figure 6.4 shows the dual mesh, advected over one timestep by a solution to the time-dependent stokes problem. An error is clearly visible at the top: the tangent velocity appears not to increase monotonically towards the top.

Figure 6.4

Semi-lagrangian advection of the dual mesh over a lid-driven cavity. It can be interpreted as a visualization of the transformation an advected field will undergo.

7. NUMERICAL RESULTS (MATLAB)

The solutions to the Stokes equations in MATLAB have been computed by MATLAB built-in solvers.

All the presented cases have been solved to machine precision, thus guaranteeing lack of overconstraint, and numerical analysis has been used to check for the correct dimension of the null-space.

7.1. LAPLACE EQUATION

The presented theory is applied to the Laplace equation. A rectangular grid, of 32x16 rectangular primal faces is used.

The bottom is isolated; set to zero normal flux. On the left and right side, constant values of opposite sign are specified on the potential. The conditions at the top side are set to either zero flux (complete isolation) or zero potential (completely unisolated).

When the top side is completely isolated, a linear gradient is obtained, according to expectation. When a zero function value is prescribed, the linear gradient gets disturbed.

The full systems of equations, including boundary conditions are solved using a simple Jacobi smoother. Convergence to machine precision is attained according to expectation, which provides numerical support for the absence of overconstraints. The convergence history for such a system is shown in figure 7.2. Further numerical inspection using MATLAB affirms that the square systems thus formulated have full rank, and if pure Neumann conditions are specified, the system is both once overconstrained and once underconstrained.

The sparsity pattern belonging for such a problem is shown in figure 7.4.

Figure 7.2

Convergence history of the residual 2-norm of Jacobi iteration without underrelaxation on the Laplace equation, including boundary conditions. The first iterations give substantial convergence, due to the elimination of high-frequency components. Asymptotic convergence on the low-frequency modes results afterwards, up to machine precision if so desired.

7.1.1. SPHERICAL DOMAIN

Most calculations have been performed over a tensor grid, or cell complex with square cells. It should be noted that this is not due to any theoretical or implementational constraints: infact, the code where the equations are formulated is completely independent of the shape of the elements and other properties of the domain under consideration; even of the dimension and intrinsic curvature of the domain. Both the theory and implementation is completely insensitive to such differences. Formulating the Stokes equations over a sphere involve the exact same mathematics, and the exact same programming steps, as in any other domain.

Presented is an example of the Laplace equation over a non-Euclidian domain. The domain is a sphere, represented as an icosahedron, which has been recursively subdivided by barycentric division three times. This yields a complex with 642 vertices, 1920 edges and 1280 faces. The discrete metric is computed in exact conformance with a spherical metric.

As has been proven, the null-space of this Laplace operator should be of rank one, which is confirmed by numerical experiment.

Figure 7.3

Contour plot of spherical harmonics, or eigenvectors of the Laplace operator on a spherical domain.

On the left, the eigenvector corresponding to the lowest nonzero eigenvalue is plotted, while the viewpoint is aligned with the plane of the circular contours. The linear gradient associated with the first spherical harmonic is clearly visible. The multiplicity of the associated eigenvalue is three, as it should be.

On the right, an eigenvector corresponding to a higher eigenvalue is plotted. The inability of the numerical eigenvector-finding algorithm to distinguish canonical modes leads to interesting and plausible patterns.

This example is provided merely as a demonstration of the claim that the obtained results are not restricted to square regular meshes, but apply to simplicial and curved meshes without conceptual complications. No further analysis is performed, but the reproduction of the linear gradient of the first spherical harmonic provides strong visual evidence for the fidelity of the solution.

Figure 7.4

Sparsity structure of the Laplace equation in first order form. Boundary conditions are shown in blue. Implementational generalizations demand the inclusion of a trivial set of equations on dual boundary flux.

Sparsity structure of the Laplace equation in second order form. A familiar Laplace stencil is seen in the interior. This system as a whole is provably diagonally dominant.

Figure 7.5

Sparsity pattern of the Stokes equations in first order form, without gradient of divergence term. Boundary conditions are shown in blue

Sparsity pattern of the Stokes equations reduced to velocity-pressure formulation. The boundary conditions on vorticity take on a nontrivial form.

7.2. STOKES EQUATIONS

The theoretical result pertaining to the boundary conditions on the Stokes equations are tested.

All the domains are square cell-complexes. Resolutions are 32x32 and 32x16 primal grid cells.

Primal cell-averaged pressure is visualized without interpolation, for implementational reasons.

Vorticity is visualized with linear interpolation between primal vertices. Flux is visualized by computing the streamfunction belonging to the incompressible flux-form, and rendering a contour plot of the result.

7.2.1. PIPE FLOW

As a basic validity check, the analytically solvable Poiseuille flow is computed.

The in and outlet are forced by a pressure differential over the left and right ends, while the top and bottom are set to zero normal flux. Tangent flux is zero everywhere on the boundary. A parabolic flow profile results, with linear pressure and vorticity profiles, according to expectation.

7.2.2. HALF PIPE FLOW

The solution is symmetric, thus it should be possible to be able to model the same problem using only half the domain. The symmetry plane is characterized by zero shear stress, thus zero vorticity. Imposing a zero vorticity constraint on the symmetry plane, demonstrates homogenous constraints on vorticity as symmetry conditions.

Indeed the problem is thus well-posed, and the lower half of the full pipe is obtained.

7.2.3. LID DRIVEN CAVITY

The lid-driven cavity is a commonly employed testcase. It has zero normal flux everywhere on the boundary, and zero tangent flux everywhere, except for one side, where a constant tangent flux is imposed.

The constancy of tangent flux can be observed in the constant spacing of flux-lines near the boundary in figures 7.8 and 7.9. A pressure singularity exists at the tangent flux discontinuity.

The obtained solution agrees with expectation: the resultant stencil in the interior of this problem has been employed many times before, as it is identical to a staggered grid finite difference discretization. All boundary conditions are essential boundary conditions, with trivial stencil.

7.2.4. HALF LID DRIVEN CAVITY

The same problem is solved on half the domain; normal flux is left unspecified at the (anti)symmetry plane, and constant pressure is instead imposed. The same solution is thus obtained.

7.2.5. FORCE-DRIVEN CAVITY

Instead of driving the cavity by prescription of a constant velocity, it can be driven by a constant shear force, or constant vorticity. Imposing constant vorticity on the boundary does indeed yield a well behaved solution.

The solution in figure 7.10 differs from the lid driven cavity in having gentler gradients. Vorticity does indeed take a constant value on the left, and the streamlines deviate from constant spacing along the driven edge, indicating non-constant tangent flux, unlike in figure 7.8.

7.2.6. HALF FORCE DRIVEN CAVITY

Again, taking only half the domain yields exactly the lower half of the square domain. This is an interesting case, as it demonstrates four different boundary conditions cooperating; constraints on pressure, vorticity, tangent flux and normal flux, or 'doubly-mixed' boundary conditions.

The sparsity pattern belonging to this problem has been plotted in figure 7.5.

7.2.7. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

In a way, no new stencils are introduced: the same stencils, motivated by discrete topology, are extended to the boundary. So we should expect the same second order convergence as these stencils are known to yield in the interior.

Convergence factors are estimated by calculating the L2 norm of error, and considering their ratio. A measure for the error is conveniently obtained in terms of pressure. Since the pressure is intimately coupled to the other solution variables, this suffices to establish the order convergence. Lower order convergence behavior in any other variable would propagate to the pressure solution.

Cells are recursively subdivided, where the linear dimensions are halved at each level of refinement. The primal pressure 2-form corresponds to integrals of pressure over a cell. If the solution is to be exact, the integral of pressure over a cell, should equal the sum of integrals of pressure over its refined subcells. The deviation from this equality is computed, and the L2 norm of the resulting relative error vector is taken. The ratio of these relative error norms should convergence to a constant value $f = (H/h)^P$, where P is the order of convergence. Thus given the recursive refinement where $H/h = 2$, $f \rightarrow 4$ implies second-order convergence.

On the pipe domain, convergence in terms of L2 norm is immediate for any level of refinement. If the method is indeed second order accurate, this is to be expected, by the absence of higher-order derivatives in the algebraic solution of pressure.

The most demanding test-case is the half force driven cavity, as it features all possible boundary stencils. Convergence factors for this problem are computed over 6 different levels of mesh-refinement. The coarsest level consist of a primal mesh having merely two square cells. After 5 levels of recursive refinement, doubling the resolution in terms of linear dimension each step, a mesh with 2048 primal 2-cells is obtained. The results of this analysis are listed in figure 7.12.

Figure 7.12

Number of recursive refinements: Coarse / Fine	L2 norm of relative error between levels	Mesh levels participating in convergence factor estimate	Convergence factor estimate f (Ratio of L2 norm)
0 / 1	6.4507	0 / 1 / 2	2.0954
1 / 2	3.0785	1 / 2 / 3	3.3828
2 / 3	0.9101	2 / 3 / 4	3.7534
3 / 4	0.2425	3 / 4 / 5	3.9227
4 / 5	0.0618		

Table of error norms

Table of convergence factors

The convergence factors rapidly approach four, which reveals second order convergence, according to expectation. Convergence deviates significantly from four at the coarsest level, which is

understandable given that the features of the solution, such as the pressure spike in the corner, are not at all resolved at these resolutions.

8. CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that ab-initio discrete mathematics has applications within fluid dynamics. Much of the work done in discrete exterior calculus is driven by applications in animation, but the mathematics thus developed are relevant to problems in engineering as well.

The notion of Poincare duality has been examined on the context of bounded domains, where it has been found to conflict with the definition of a topological primitive. Augmenting Poincare duality such as to satisfy key topological definitions, yields a definite procedure for closing dual manifolds.

The algebraic structure of this dual boundary takes on meaning in the discrete calculus setting as additional variables. Introducing matching equations in such a way as to restore the symmetric character of the equations in the interior, leads to a definite recipe for the most general form of boundary conditions permissible.

In the context of the Laplace equation, the stated procedure leads to the Robin boundary condition. In the context of the Stokes equations, two boundary conditions are obtained which agree with physical intuition, and recent findings in the context of continuum calculus.

The route by which these conclusions are reached are much shorter and accessible than the alternative. Aside from this theoretical simplification, the symmetry argument employed naturally enables the use and design of efficient iterative solvers for the complete system of equations, including boundary conditions.

Implementations of the presented theory function according to expectations derived from these theoretical arguments. The equations obtained are numerically well-behaved, and second-order convergence has been demonstrated.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

The presented arguments concerning boundary conditions for linear systems of equations may serve as a starting point for insight into boundary conditions for more general equations of fluid dynamics, such as compressible or non-linear equations. These boundary conditions have already been effectively implemented and have been found to work in the context of the Navier-Stokes equations [1], although no case is made for these boundary conditions holding in general, nor is this directly obvious. A theoretical investigation thereof might prove insightful.

Despite having invested much effort into obtaining a unified diagonally dominant form of the Stokes equations including boundary conditions, similar to the one found for the Laplace equations, this goal has not been attained. Yet the fact that it is possible for the equations in the interior, and the similarity of the boundary conditions to the interior, do suggest this should be possible. One idea towards this goal, which has occurred too late to be implemented is thus: Eliminating equations from the system is discussed as a theoretical argument, but all transformations which have been tried are 'non-intrusive' in the sense that the elements of the system matrix, nor its size have been altered. If the symmetry-violating terms are actually eliminated, then it would seem distributed relaxation can be applied directly.

Applications outside fluid dynamics seem likely, most notably other systems of equations that can be fully formulated in vector calculus, such as Maxwell equations of electrodynamics.

The relation between symmetry and boundary conditions emphasized in this thesis might yield parallels that extend to other discretization schemes. Restoring the symmetry inherent to the interior of the domain is a principle which might be applicable to more general systems of linear equations.

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APPENDIX: IMPLEMENTATION

Once compelling aspect of DEC is the elegance with which the concepts can be translated into computer code. One can easily impose a division between meshing, formulation of equations, and solutions of equations, without loss of efficiency or generality.

Implementation has been divided between MATLAB and C++. To satisfy the demands of the semi-Lagrangian method which has been partially implemented, C++ was chosen over MATLAB for its provision of the more complex data structures needed. An associative dynamics data structure has been implemented, allowing for the storage and querying of mesh data in an efficient manner. Operations such as `edge_vertex[someedge, somevertex] = -1` are supported in constant time, and so is access to rows and column of this structure. `edge_vertex[somevertex]` returns a view to a container iterating over edges associated with said vertex. Lazy set operations, such as intersection and difference have been defined in terms of `filtered_views` over such sets, leading to an efficient implementation of the required algorithms.

The same things can be accomplished using MATLAB vector operations, but extracting the rows and columns of a matrix is not both possible in constant time, given a compressed or coordinate matrix format. These operations are needed in some of the meshing algorithms, and as such, implementations in MATLAB are prohibitively expensive for anything but small meshes.

The C++ implementation is less than ten thousands of lines of code, but it makes heavy use of template programming. Experimenting with new linear algebraic techniques for the boundary conditions proved unworkable, as the compilation time without any optimizations was several minutes. Especially the MTL4 library seemed problematic in this regard. Therefore, the C++ project has been abandoned in favor of a more easily editable and debugable MATLAB implementation, which is better suited to prototyping algorithms.

Two custom classes have been written for MATLAB, dealing with sparse block-matrices. The 'block' class holds 3x3 sparse matrices, and utilities for access of subblocks and other manipulations. The 'system' class holds a variable number of 3x3 blocks, and provides functions for their assembly and transformation.

Given nothing but a properly formed primal-dual complex and their Hodges, and a set of coefficient vectors for the boundary conditions, the following is literally all code specific to the formulation of the Stokes equations, including well posed boundary conditions.

```

S(1,1)(:, :) = -mesh.hodge.P0D2;
S(1,2)(:, :) = mesh.hodge.P0D2 * mesh.dual.d21;           %curl of velocity

S(2,1)(:, :) = mesh.primal.d10 * mesh.hodge.P0D2;       %curl of vorticity
S(2,1)(3,2) = spdiag(BC.tangent.neumann) * S(1,2)(2,3); %cotangent vorticity
S(2,2)(3,3) = spdiag(BC.tangent.dirichlet);              %tangent velocity
S(2,3)(:, :) = mesh.hodge.P1D1 * mesh.dual.d10;         %gradient of pressure
S(2)(3,1) = BC.tangent.RHS;

S(3,2)(:, :) = mesh.primal.d21 * mesh.hodge.P1D1;       %divergence of velocity
S(3,2)(3,2) = spdiag(BC.normal.neumann) * S(2,3)(2,3); %normal velocity
S(3,3)(3,3) = spdiag(BC.normal.dirichlet);               %normal pressure
S(3)(3,1) = BC.normal.RHS;

```

The code for the 3D stokes equations, would look exactly the same aside from the indices of the Hodges and exterior derivatives. Given this assembly of equations, $S.A \setminus S.b$ would be enough to find a solution, although applying a reduction transformation first, and using a more effective solver is of course preferable.

Meshes are generated by recursive subdivision of given initial configuration. This is a fairly complex algorithm, involving many iterations over the rows and columns of the incidence matrices. On the other hand, the transformation of a mesh into into a primal-dual complex involving the substructuring of the topology matrices can be implemented in a few elegant lines of code

```

%dual topology, primal topology transposed
dual.T01 = Transpose(primal.T12);
dual.T12 = Transpose(primal.T01);

%augment block with 3,3 term
dual.T01 = Augment(dual.T01, D0, D1);
dual.T12 = Augment(dual.T12, D1, D2);

%dual boundary is formed by primal boundary transposed
dual.T01(3,3) = Transpose(primal.T01(2,2));

% close open ends: deduce {3,2}-term
dual.T01(3,2) = -spdiag(sum(dual.T01(1,2), 1));
dual.T12(3,2) = -dual.T01(3,2);

```

Initial implementations of these concepts, before realizing the simplifying linear algebraic view on boundary terms, were like the subdivision algorithms, hundreds of lines of complicated algorithms involving many set operations and lot of bookkeeping, in order to connect the closing dual topological terms while respecting sign conventions.

It has been found that considerable portions of the mesh generation/subdivision code can also be recast in terms of simple linear algebra as well, although I have no succeeded in pushing the approach all the way.